

Article

Galloping Across Realms: Scientific and Symbolic Interpretations of the Eurasian “Heavenly Horse” and Other Galloping Horses in Art

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Abstract

This article explores the depiction of galloping horses in ancient art, focusing on a Greco-Bactrian gilt bronze finial known as the “Heavenly Horse.” By systematically classifying artistic gallop motifs—rearing gallop, flying gallop, landing gallop, and the anatomically accurate V-gallop—the study traces the evolution of equine imagery across Eurasia. Detailed analysis of the Heavenly Horse finial shows that its pose, musculature, and anatomical features closely correspond to the true suspension phase of a horse’s gallop, a finding supported by modern motion studies. High-resolution 3D scanning, surface diagnostics, and computational modeling indicate that the sculpture’s mass distribution was intentionally designed for dynamic balance and realism. The artifact’s stylistic features, such as the frontal forehead protuberance and S-shaped neck, align with descriptions of elite horse breeds in ancient Chinese and Central Asian sources. Symbolic motifs, including the vine-and-cloud scroll, further connect the object to broader Eurasian traditions of imperial and celestial symbolism. Comparative analysis with Saka and Chinese artifacts highlights both shared conventions and unique technical achievements. The study demonstrates how the Heavenly Horse finial integrates empirical observation, artistic tradition, and symbolic meaning, reflecting the exchange of ideas and technologies along the Silk Road.

Keywords: galloping horse; equine biomechanics; V-gallop; Greco-Bactrian art; Heavenly Horse (Tianma); ancient sculpture; Silk Road; cultural exchange; Ferghana horse; Saka animal style

1. Introduction

Since the publication of early chronophotographic series on horse locomotion (Stillman 1888; Marey 1898; Muybridge 1902; Gray 1953), scholars have recognized that artistic representations of galloping horses often diverge from the true biomechanics of equine motion. Numerous commentators have pointed out inaccuracies in depictions of the galloping horse, both in ancient and more recent art (Waring 1882; Stillman 1888, pp. 102–4; Dehousset 1902, p. 163; Lankester 1913; Edgerton 1936; Mastandrea and Kennedy 2018; Papacosta 2018; Kennedy et al. 2020). Two principal motifs—commonly encountered across cultures—have been subject to particular scrutiny: the “rearing gallop,” often shown with both hind legs grounded and the front legs raised, and the “flying gallop,” in which all four legs are off the ground and extended out to the front and rear (in a suspended phase). Both types, although visually dynamic, bear little resemblance

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to the phases documented in chronophotographic studies, where the actual gallop rarely exhibits these positions.

Nevertheless, as this body of research has demonstrated, some phases resembling these stylized motifs can occur at moments when horses launch into a gallop from rest, leap over obstacles, or perform sudden maneuvers during activities like polo or warfare. In addition to these conventions, more realistic portrayals can be found, including the rarely depicted “V-gallop” or flexed suspension phase, where all limbs are flexed beneath the body during full suspension—a pose confirmed by motion photography but seldom realized in ancient art.

This article undertakes a systematic review and independent classification of gallop types in art, focusing on the rearing gallop, flying gallop, landing gallop, and V-gallop (flexed suspension), and uses a broad range of examples from different periods and regions to establish a reproducible visual baseline for each motif. The analysis not only considers artistic conventions but also the ways in which artists have, at times, directly observed and accurately rendered equine movement.

A central focus of the study is the Greco-Bactrian gilt bronze finial known as the “Heavenly Horse,” which offers a rare and anatomically precise depiction of the V-gallop suspension phase. Through high-resolution 3D scanning and biomechanical assessment, we argue that the sculpture’s pose, musculature, and anatomical features are consistent with careful empirical observation of horse locomotion long before these phases were scientifically documented through modern motion studies. The finial’s elongated forms, swirling patterns, frontal protuberance, and naturalistic details evoke a blend of Central Asian, Scythian-Saka, Hellenistic, and Chinese cultural references, which are further explored through comparative analysis with Saka, Chinese, and other Eurasian artifacts.

This study has three main aims. First, it establishes a clear and reproducible visual and anatomical baseline for gallop poses in art, with special attention to the realistic V-gallop. Second, it confirms the V-gallop in three dimensions on the Greco-Bactrian gilt bronze finial, using this as evidence of the artisan’s empirical knowledge of equine motion. Third, it interprets the cultural-historical significance of the so-called Tianma (“Heavenly Horse”) by linking the finial’s form and iconography to Han dynasty texts and Central Asian lore, breed-associated and iconographic features such as the frontal protuberance (jibbah), the vine-and-cloud motif, and patterns of artistic exchange at the Greek-Saka interface. Notably, the third aim depends on the preceding two: the cultural significance of the Heavenly Horse can only be fully understood by first establishing a visual and anatomical baseline and then confirming the empirical accuracy and intent behind the finial’s depiction.

Methodologically, the article applies advanced digital protocols (including mirrored-mesh asymmetry, power spectral density screening, mesh-density heterogeneity, and inertia-tensor analysis) to document anatomical form, surface treatment, workshop practice, and balance, extending recent scan-based approaches in the study of ancient sculpture.

By situating the Heavenly Horse finial within the broader history of horse exchange, symbolism, and technological innovation along the Silk Road, the study highlights how the representation of galloping horses served not only esthetic or decorative purposes but also articulated deeper social, political, and cosmological meanings. The motif’s evolution—from stylized to realistic forms—mirrors cross-cultural interactions and the dynamic relationship between observation, skill, and ideology in ancient Eurasian societies.

In sum, the article demonstrates that artistic depictions of the galloping horse, while often stylized, include notable examples of anatomical accuracy and technical sophistication. The Greco-Bactrian Heavenly Horse finial, in particular, stands as a key artifact for understanding the intersection of empirical observation, artistic tradition, and symbolic meaning in early Eurasian art.

2. The Galloping Horse in Art

To establish the comparative basis for the later analysis, this section first examines the galloping horse as a broader visual and anatomical problem in art. The aim is not simply to provide background examples, but to define a typology of gallop motifs (rearing gallop, flying gallop, landing gallop, and V-gallop) across different artistic media, materials, chronological periods, and geographical regions. Because painting, relief, and free-standing sculpture impose different formal constraints, the discussion distinguishes where relevant between linear contour, shallow depth, and three-dimensional problems of volume, support, mass, and balance. Chronology and geography are used to clarify how these visual formulas recur and vary across Eurasian traditions, while questions of cultural transmission are raised only where they are supported by existing scholarship. This typological framework then provides the basis for assessing why the Heavenly Horse finial is significant as a rare three-dimensional rendering of the V-gallop suspension phase.

Artistically the horse's gallop is typically depicted in two main ways, whether in a painting or sculpture: (1) the "rearing gallop," where both hind legs are on the ground (usually aligned perpendicular to the horse's forward movement), and the front legs are lifted and either flexed or extended forward (Figure 1); and (2) the "flying gallop," where all four legs are off the ground, with the hind legs extended backward and the front legs flexed or extended forward (Figure 2) (Reinach 1901, p. 7; MacIntosh 1995, p. 51). The rearing gallop motif is especially common in Western art, while the flying gallop is more frequently seen in Eastern pieces.

Figure 1. Example of artistic rendering of horse in a "rearing gallop" (illustration by Author).

Figure 2. Example of artistic rendering of horse in a "flying gallop" (illustration by Author).

Two exquisite statuary traditions represent these contrasting depictions of a gallop in ancient art. The rearing gallop motif is exemplified by the Jockey of Artemision, a bronze equestrian statue discovered in 1926 at Cape Artemision near Euboea (Figure 3). Though found in pieces, it was restored and is now displayed at the National Archaeological Museum in Athens (Hemingway 2004, pp. 35–40; Scherz and Stribling 2017, pl. 7, p. 5).¹ Likely created to celebrate a horse race victory, it dates to around 140–200 BC.² In spite of any inaccuracies due to its representation of a rider on a horse in a rearing gallop, and so with both hind legs on the ground (see below; and see Hemingway 2004, p. 106, who argues that the front legs are too short), the statue realistically portrays a racing horse in motion: front legs are highly extended, the mouth and nose wide open and displaced due to air resistance encountered during the gallop, the muscles and tendons are tensed in exertion, and even foreleg chestnuts are rendered (Hemingway 2004, pp. 49–52, 92–94). The pose, with hind legs grounded, may have aided the statue’s stability, as suggested by the thicker bronze in the hind legs, although there is no definitive evidence it was mounted on a base (Hemingway 2004, p. 140).

Figure 3. Hellenistic Jockey of Artemision equestrian bronze statue displaying horse in “rearing gallop” pose (Jockey of Artemision on a red background, submitted by N. Kitsakis on 31 October 2024. Licensed for use under CC-BY 4.0, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

The flying gallop motif is well represented in Tang terracotta figurines of women polo players on horseback (ca. 675–763), discovered in Qian, Shaanxi Province, China since the 1960s (Figure 4) (Cooke 2000, pl. 127, 133, pp. 142, 146; Pickeral 2006, p. 196; Choi 2017; Sung 2022, pl. 6, p. 27; Shea 2023, pl. 4).³ These vividly glazed figurines show riders on polo horses in a flying gallop, with the horse’s musculature and ligaments portrayed quite realistically. Although depicted with all four legs fully extended and off the ground, this pose does not represent an actual phase of a horse’s gallop (see below).

Figure 4. Tang Dynasty statue of female polo player, Musée Guimet, Paris, inv. no. MA 6117 (“Female polo player Guimet MA6117,” created by M.L. Nguyen on 25 June 2017. Licensed for use under CC BY 4.0, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2.1. The Rearing Gallop

The most common portrayal of the galloping horse in ancient Western art, as Reinach (1901) noted, was the “rearing gallop,” with both front feet in the air (flexed or extended) and both hind feet on the ground and typically located directly across from each other and perpendicular to the line of forward motion (Figures 1 and 3). This motif appears in some of the earliest horse images, such as Paleolithic cave paintings from Font-de-Gaume and Lascaux, France (ca. 17,300–17,000 BC) (Pickeral 2006, p. 7; Áldez-Sánchez and García-Viñas 2019, pl. 5g, 5j, p. 7), and later on in ancient Egyptian, Assyrian, Greek, Roman, and medieval art.

It achieves prominence in Egyptian paintings (ca. 1500–1290 BC) depicting Pharaohs on chariots pulled by horses (Figure 5) (Reinach 1901, pl. 8, 11, pp. 15–16; Pickeral 2006, p. 41; Feldman and Sauvage 2010, pl. 19–25, pp. 121–26; Tatomir 2014, p. 330; Delpeut 2021, pl. 10, 16, pp. 31, 36).⁴ These Egyptian portrayals seem to have influenced the similar depiction of horses in a rearing gallop in Assyrian gypsum reliefs from Nimrud and Nineveh, Iraq (ca. 728–635 BC) (Johns 2006, p. 34; Agüera Carmona and Cruz 2021, pl. 4, p. 5), which in turn likely influenced the depiction of Persian riders on horseback on the terracotta Bhir Mound from Taxila, Pakistan (ca. 175–25 BC) (Almagor 2021, figs. 2–5 and 13; Minardi 2022, pl. 1–2, 4, 6–7, pp. 124, 127). The depth available in these carved stone reliefs allows clearer depictions of multiple horses side-by-side in the rearing gallop and more anatomical details.⁵

An Oriental influence is apparent in regard to the paintings on Greek amphoras (ca. 635–400 BC), rendered to honor victors in horse and chariot races at the Panathenaic Games (Figure 6) (Markman 1969; Baskett 2006, p. 38; Johns 2006, p. 20; Scherz and Stribling 2017, pl. 5, 8, 53, 55, pp. 5, 7, 73, 75, and in their Appendix pl. 11, 20, 60, 62–63, 67–68, pp. 87, 93, 122–29; Delpeut and Willekes 2023, pl. 3, 13), which likewise show many horses in a rearing gallop in unison.⁶

Figure 5. Rearing gallop as seen in facsimile of Egyptian New Kingdom chariot hunt rendered in Tomb of Userhat (TT 56) located in Thebes, Egypt (photograph by Author of inv. no. 30.4.42 from Gallery 135 in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA).

Figure 6. Rearing gallop as seen in Classical Greek depiction of battle between Greeks and Amazons (photograph by Author of inv. no. 07.286.84 from Gallery 153 in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA).

In fact, it became common to produce equestrian artworks that depicted riders and rulers on horseback in a rearing gallop in the Hellenistic period (ca. 340–100 BC), which

occurs on minted coins (Antikas 2015, pl. 13), various stone reliefs, stelae, and statues (Gonteva et al. 1979–2015; Dimitrova 2002; Boteva 2016, pl. 1–4, pp. 318–19),⁷—notably a marble relief showing Alexander the Great hunting on horseback discovered at the stadium of Messene, Greece (Kazarow 1938),⁸ and a bronze statue of Alexander the Great on Bucephalus from Herculaneum (ca. 100 BC),⁹ possibly a copy of the Granicos monument of 330 BC (Johns 2006, p. 78; Pickeral 2006, p. 67; Scherz and Stribling 2017, pl. 48, p. 62; Siano et al. 2017, pl. 44.1a, p. 372). There was also an extensive tradition of Parthian fired clay reliefs (ca. 240 BC–200 AD) displaying warriors riding horses in a rearing gallop, allowing for 3D depictions of multiple riders on horseback (Baskett 2006, p. 39; Johns 2006, p. 48; Pickeral 2006, p. 34).¹⁰

As has been noted, though Rome captured Greece politically, Greece in turn impacted Rome culturally, and the rearing gallop motif is widespread in regions under Roman control. It appears in a marble relief of Tiberius Flavius Miccalus (ca. 25 BC) from Kamaradere, Perinthus, Turkey;¹¹ an Italian terracotta relief of a chariot race (ca. 75 AD) (Pickeral 2006, p. 151);¹² bronze statues recovered from the theater of Herculaneum (79 AD), likely copied from earlier Hellenistic artworks;¹³ a bronze equestrian statue (ca. 100) from Tigring, Kärnten, Austria, in the equestrian statue of Domitian, i.e., the *Equus Domitiani* (ca. 96) (Baskett 2006, pp. 14, 42–43; Johns 2006, pp. 52, 56–57).¹⁴ Such depictions in relief or statuary allowed for realistic dynamic depictions of the horse facial anatomy and body musculature.

Medieval and Renaissance art commonly featured the rearing gallop in depictions of nobles on horseback. This occurred in the Bayeux Tapestry (ca. 1070) (Reinach 1901, pl. 34, p. 26; Sundkvist 2022),¹⁵ a marble relief at the San Zeno Maggiore Church in Verona, Italy (ca. 1100), and on the noble seals of Philip I of Alsace (1177) and Robert Fitzwalter (ca. 1215) (Johns 2006, p. 96).¹⁶ The rearing gallop is especially prevalent in medieval and Renaissance illuminated manuscripts, including the Aberdeen Bestiary (ca. 1200),¹⁷ Der Stricker's *Karl der Große* (ca. 1300),¹⁸ the *Taymouth Hours* (ca. 1325–1335),¹⁹ a picture of Clovis defeating the Alemanni from the *Grandes Chroniques de France* (ca. 1332–1350),²⁰ jousting knights in René de Anjou's *Livre de tournois* (1460),²¹ the *Roman du Saint Graal* (ca. 1450) (Pickeral 2006, p. 197),²² and the *Talbot-Shrewsbury Book* (1444–1445).²³

It is often the case in art that multiple horses pulling a chariot or wagon are shown in a rearing gallop with their legs in exactly the same phase, such as all having hind legs on the ground and front legs flexed identically. In reality, however, horses pulling a chariot or wagon together are often in different phases of the gallop at a particular point in time.

2.2. The Flying Gallop

The “flying gallop” motif (Figure 2), wherein all the limbs are off the ground (i.e., in a suspended phase) and the horse's legs are extended out to the front and rear (or splayed), was, as we have seen, quite common in early Chinese art, before making its way into Western art beginning in the late eighteenth century (Reinach 1901, pp. 11, 33–34, 40, 42–43, 56–57, 60–64, 90–92; Pickeral 2006, pp. 205, 237, 241, 250).

The flying gallop motif can be seen in Qin Dynasty murals (ca. 215 BC) from Xianyang Palace, before becoming frequent in Han and Eastern Han period murals, reliefs, and stelae (ca. 150–220) (Hung 1998, pl. 1a, p. 22; Bishop 1918, pl. 81, p. 252; Fernald 1935, pl. 4.7; Linduff 2006; Tao 2019), and then continuing in murals from the Wei and Jin Dynasties (220–420 AD) in Jiayuguan City, Gansu. Such portrayals of the heavenly horse seem to have influenced Korean tomb paintings (ca. 400–500 AD) in Deokheung-ri, Gyeongju (Cheonmachong Tomb of the Heavenly Horse), and Goguryeo Muyongchong (Ahn 2015, figs. 14 and 20).

The motif is especially prominent in Tang Dynasty terracotta figurines and paintings of polo players from Qian, Shaanxi Province (ca. 650–750 AD) (Figure 7) (Cooke 2000, pl. 127, 133, pp. 142, 146; Pickeral 2006, p. 196; Choi 2017; Sung 2022, pl. 6, p. 27; Shea 2023, pl. 4).²⁴ Notably, the flying gallop is seen in two of Emperor Taizong’s six steed bluestone reliefs (ca. 636 AD), now exhibited at the Zhao Mausoleum in Shaanxi, China (Bishop 1918, pl. 89, 91–92, pp. 261, 264–65).²⁵

Figure 7. Flying gallop from Chinese Tang Dynasty as seen on painting on West Wall of tomb of Prince Zhang Huai at the Qianling Mausoleum (ca. 706), Xi’an, China (Public domain photograph by Tang Li Xian Mu Bi Hua, Shanxi sheng bo wu guan (Beijing: Wen Wu Chu Ban She, 1974), pl. 15).

The flying gallop motif continues on in Chinese art and is later found in tomb paintings at the Qianling Mausoleum (7th–8th centuries), Huang Zongdao’s stag hunt scroll (Northern Song, ca. 1120 AD) (Figure 8),²⁶ Yuan Dynasty tomb murals and paintings by Chen Jizhi (ca. 1300) from Luogetai, Hengshan county, Shaanxi; and Ming Dynasty hunting scenes (ca. 1600).²⁷

Figure 8. Flying gallop from Chinese Northern Song Dynasty as seen in “Stag hunt” painting by Huang Zongdao (ca. 1120) (Open Access image from The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, Edward Elliott Family Collection, Purchase, The Dillon Fund Gift, 1982, inv. no. 1982.3.1, <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/39938>, accessed on 17 May 2025).

Reinach did note that the “flying gallop” motif appears on occasion in the West, such as on Aegean tombstones, swords, and signet rings from Mycenae, Greece (ca. 1600–1550 BC) (Kelder 2020, pl. 7a-b),²⁸ Archaic Cretan clay pithoi (ca. 660–630 BC) (Scherz and Stribling 2017, pl. 9, p. 86), Sasanian Persian limestone reliefs (ca. 325–375 AD) (Figure 9), as well as in some medieval murals and illuminated manuscripts (ca. 750–1600) (Bishop 1918, pl. 84–85, pp. 255–56).²⁹ He was probably too quick, however, to dismiss the “flying gallop” in Assyrian and Egyptian art, suggesting such depictions were actually variations of the rearing gallop, either with horses kicking out their hind legs or barely touching the ground with their hooves (Reinach 1901, pl. 13, p. 23; see Reinach 1901, pl. 7, 28, pp. 14, 22; for a contrasting view see Spruyt 2022, pl. 9, p. 17). However, depictions of a chariot horse on a golden bowl from Ugarit, Syria (ca. 1400–1300 BC)³⁰ and an Assyrian marble relief from Nineveh, Iraq (ca. 640 BC),³¹ arguably show horses in a flying gallop, though the latter depicts a horse being chased by a predator, supporting Reinach’s point. And in fact, there are some pretty clear renderings of the flying gallop in ancient Egyptian art, such as a rider from the tomb of Horemheb (ca. 1325 BC) in Saqqara (Delpout 2021, pl. 15, p. 36);³² an Egyptian ivory whip handle shaped as a horse (ca. 1390–1352 BC) (Figure 10) (Kelder 2020, pl. 6, p. 65);³³ and a tool from the tomb of Kha (ca. 1350 BC) in Deir el-Medina (Kelder 2020, pl. 2, p. 65), whereby the tradition may have influenced Assyrian art.

Figure 9. Flying gallop as seen in Sasanian Persian depiction of a king hunting (ca. 485–530) (Open Access image from The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, Fletcher Fund, 1934, inv. no. 34.33, <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/322973>, accessed on 17 May 2025).

Again, contrary to Reinach’s claim that the flying gallop is absent in Roman and medieval art, it does appear in some cases, such as bronze horse and rider chariot attachments from Herculaneum (79 AD)³⁴ a mosaic showing Bellerophon riding the winged horse Pegasus from a Roman villa at Mud Hole, Boxford, England (ca. 325–375) (Beeson 1996), and even in the Bayeux Tapestry (ca. 1070) (Figure 11).³⁵ Nonetheless, Reinach’s general view holds: flying gallop depictions are rare in Western art and much more common in Oriental art, possibly influenced by earlier Aegean and Cretan works (Kelder 2020).

Figure 10. Horse in flying gallop from ivory whip handle from the New Kingdom of Egypt (ca. 1390–1352 BC). (Open Access image from The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, Purchase, Edward S. Harkness Gift, 1926, inv. no. 26.7.1293, <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/544853>, accessed on 18 May 2025).

Figure 11. Bayeux Tapestry, scene 54 depicting battle of Hastings with horse at left in a flying gallop (Public Domain).

2.3. *The Realistic Gallop and the Landing Gallop*

As pointed out earlier, several scholars have seen such artistic depictions of horses in a rearing gallop or flying gallop as wildly inaccurate (Waring 1882; Stillman 1888, pp. 102–4; Dehoussset 1902, p. 163; Lankester 1913; Edgerton 1936; Mastandrea and Kennedy 2018, Papacosta 2018; Kennedy et al. 2020). And, in truth, similar phases of the gallop are rarely observed in chronophotographic or videographic series of a galloping horse (see Figure 12). However, it is not entirely clear that such portrayals of the gallop are failures of human observation.

It is true that the “rearing gallop” most resembles not a horse galloping, but instead a horse rearing up in the air on its haunches, lowering its center of gravity, and lifting its front feet off the ground; or perhaps a horse performing an advanced dressage movement, such as a levade or pesade in place, a courbette or terre-a-terre with slight forward motion; or a horse trampling an enemy on the ground in front of it. Still, a phase resembling the “rearing gallop” can be seen in a horse launching itself into the gallop from a standstill at the start of a race (Figure 13). This can also occur in a horse screeching to a halt, rapidly changing orientation, and launching itself into a gallop in a new direction, as can occur in a polo match (Figure 14); or in barrel racing where Quarter horses have to quickly maneuver around barrels by stopping, turning, switching directions (i.e., the rollback), and then launching into a gallop in the opposite direction. And though not seen in the chronophotographic series of the galloping horse in Muybridge or Stillman (Muybridge 1902, pp. 164, 171–81; Stillman 1888, pl. 7, p. 92), Marey’s series of a galloping horse does show a moment where both front feet are off the ground and the hindfeet are on the ground at the same time and

not too far apart (though not as lined up in a coronal plane or transverse to the direction of travel) (Figure 15) (Marey 1898, pl. 1, p. 25).

Figure 12. Series of thoroughbred horse galloping at 15.6 m/s (Public Domain work, Photograph by Muybridge (1902, p. 173)).

Figure 13. Thoroughbred horses launching into a gallop out of the starting gate, thereby entering into a phase resembling the “rearing gallop (photograph licensed under CC-by-2.0 from M.J. Boswell, Horse Race Starting Gate, 23 June 2014, [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Horse_Race_Starting_Gate_\(14304242538\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Horse_Race_Starting_Gate_(14304242538).jpg), accessed on 27 May 2025).

Figure 14. Polo Argentino horse changing direction and rapidly accelerating in a polo match, in a pose resembling a “rearing gallop.” Photograph by Author.

Figure 15. Galloping phase of a horse resembling a rearing gallop (Public Domain photograph from Marey (1898, pl. 1, p. 25)).

Again, it is true that the “flying gallop” most resembles not a galloping horse, but instead a horse in mid-flight that is leaping over an obstacle (Fredricson et al. 1980;

Leach and Ormrod 1984; Leach et al. 1984; Moore et al. 1995; Powers and Harrison 2000); or certain advanced dressage movements such as a Lipizzaner performing a capriole with the hind legs extended; or a horse performing a “Spanish jump” and extending both fore and hind legs; or a horse more naturally leaping forward and kicking its hind legs back in self-defense (see Pickeral 2006, pp. 84, 202). Still, there is a phase of the gallop in which both front and rear legs are extended, albeit not to the extent depicted in art, nor with all four limbs off the ground at once, nor with the limbs equally advanced (Figure 16). Moreover, on occasion some horses (such as Secretariat) can engage in a very fast transverse gallop wherein three legs (including the two hind legs) are off the ground at the same time and all extended (Figure 17), and there may even be two periods of full suspension where all four legs are off the ground and extended, though evidence is inconclusive at the moment (Owens et al. 2015). Additionally, a horse in a gallop which then leaps over an obstacle can certainly resemble one in the flying gallop shown in art. Finally, lighter animals, especially those such as a dog or deer who perform a rotary gallop, often have a phase wherein all four legs are off the ground at the same time and extended to the front and rear (Muybridge 1902, pp. 189, 193). So, the portrayal of horses in a flying gallop may not be wholly inaccurate biomechanically speaking.

Figure 16. Phases of gallop in racing thoroughbreds somewhat resembling a flying gallop (photograph by Author).

That being said, in many artistic renderings of the horse in a flying gallop, the horse is portrayed rushing into battle, pulling a chariot, transporting a human at high velocity, or chasing prey in a hunt, without any obstacle to be leapt over in sight. In such situations a flying gallop is highly unlikely to have actually occurred. So, there are grounds for criticizing the realism of the way the gallop is portrayed in art, especially in its flying gallop form. We must not forget, however, that art is not necessarily directed at realistic portrayals, but instead may be focused on such things as dynamically depicting speed or motion. Indeed, in art, artists may blend phases or stylize limb positions for compositional or symbolic reasons (see discussion in Sections 3.3 and 4.2).

In any case, more realistic portrayals of the gallop do occur in ancient art that closely match the typical landing phases of the gallop seen in chronophotographic or videographic studies of the horse. Such artistic depictions depict the initial ground contact phase of a gallop fairly accurately, wherein one or two hind feet touch down upon the terrain and are not aligned but instead separated spatially on the coronal plane, while both front feet remain off the ground (Figure 12) (Muybridge 1902, pp. 173, 175, 177, 179).

Figure 17. Fast gallop with single-foot suspension phase, resembling a flying gallop in a Polo Argentino horse. Photograph by Author.

In the West, such realistic representations of the “landing gallop” occur in Egyptian art, such as paintings from the tomb of Mahu and from tomb 9 of El Amarna (ca. 1340 BC) (Delpeut 2021, pl. 14, p. 35). Such Egyptian portrayals may have influenced the renderings of a similar “landing gallop” in Classical Greek coins and pottery (ca. 520–289 BC) (Figure 18), which quite often portrayed the winged horse Pegasus (Johns 2006, p. 168; Scherz and Stribling 2017, pl. 2, 4, 13–16, 19, 47–48, 68, 73, pp. 2, 4, 88–92, 112–13, 129–32),³⁶ and on the frieze (ca. 438–423 BC) of the North Wall of the Parthenon in Athens (Pickeral 2006, p. 38; Scherz and Stribling 2017, pl. 43, p. 56). In the Hellenistic period, examples of the realistic landing phase of the galloping horse can be found in Scythian, Thracian, and Greco-Bactrian art (ca. 330–125 BC) (Antikas 2015, pl. 14, 17–18); in a floor mosaic showing the battle of Issos featuring Macedonians against Persians from Pompei (ca. 310 BC),³⁷ and in an equestrian statue of a noble on horseback found on the island of Melos (ca. 100 BC).³⁸ Later Persian art from Iran (ca. 1335–1600) also portrays the landing phase of a galloping horse fairly realistically (Johns 2006, p. 92; Curtis et al. 2012).³⁹

We find similar realistic representations of the landing phase of the gallop in ancient Chinese art, including Eastern Han paintings of chariots and horses (ca. 125–200) on a tomb in Luoyang, Henan Province, China (Figure 19);⁴⁰ a tomb in the Mausoleum of Qin Shi Huang, Xi’an, Shaanxi Province, China; tomb M23 in Shenmu, Shaanxi Province, China; and a tomb in Anping, Hebei Province, China (Wallace 2018, pl. 8.1, 8.2, pp. 198–99; Sung 2022, Cat 5 and pl. 1–3, pp. 21–22).⁴¹ Later Oriental depictions of realistic gallop landing phases occur in a painting of a Mongol archer riding a horse (ca. 1450–1550) (Pickeral 2006, p. 13),⁴² and in several Edo period scroll paintings (18th century [?]) of riders on horseback, likely depicting the goings-on at an equestrian school from the Konshai region of Honshu Island, Japan (Ramey 2024, pp. 41–43). Here, such paintings of wide scenes perhaps allowed for realistic study and portrayal of a galloping horse.

Figure 18. Realistic Roman portrayal of horses galloping (ca. 27 BC–68 AD). Perhaps, however, based on earlier Greek model of horses rearing to a halt. (Open Access image from The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, Fletcher Fund, 1926, inv. no. 26.60.31, <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/252498>, accessed on 18 May 2025).

Figure 19. Realistic portrayal of gallop landing phase in fresco from tomb in Luoyang, China (ca. 125–200) (CC-by-SA-all, photo by Gary Lee Todd, 12 June 2008, https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Eastern_Han_Dynasty_tomb_fresco_of_chariots_horses_and_men_Luoyang.jpg, accessed on 18 May 2025).

There is one other phase of the actual gallop of the horse, however, that is rarely represented in art, the typical phase of full suspension wherein all four legs are off

the ground at once. When this phase occurs, all four limbs are not extended as in a “flying gallop,” but rather flexed and bunched in what we will call the V-gallop or flexed gallop (Figures 12, 20 and 21) (see Stillman 1888, pl. 3, p. 89; Muybridge 1902, pp. 173, 175, 177, 179). Amazingly, an early V-gallop is represented in a cave painting (ca. 15,000 BC) from La Paloma, Asturias, Spain (Pigeaud 2007, pl. 4j, p. 415), and it is found in horse ornaments (CA. 500 BC) from the Ordos Desert of China (Carter 1957, pl. 17b, p. 93 and pl. 18b, p. 94). The V-gallop scarcely appears again in Western Europe or Eastern art until it occurs in scattered Renaissance illuminated manuscripts, such as in *Le livre et la vraie hystoire du bon roy Alixandre* (ca. 1420–1425),⁴³ and in later nineteenth century art influenced by the reproduction of chronophotographic series of the horse gallop by Muybridge and others. However, it does appear in a particular Hellenistic Greco-Bactrian statue that will be the focus of the rest of this article.

Figure 20. Realistic V-gallop or flexed gallop phase of horse (illustration by Author).

Figure 21. Polo Argentino horse in V-gallop or flexed gallop (photograph by Author).

2.4. Typological Summary of Gallop Motifs

The four gallop types discussed above are summarized in Table 1. This typological overview distinguishes between conventional artistic formulas and more anatomically realistic renderings of equine motion, providing the comparative framework for the analysis of the Heavenly Horse finial in the following sections.

Table 1. Summary of the four gallop types discussed in Section 2.

Types of Gallop	Description
1. Rearing Gallop (double aligned hind contact; forelimbs elevated and flexed or extended)	The horse is shown pushing off from aligned hind legs with the front legs raised. This is a common artistic convention in many Western cultures. This type appears regularly in different media and time periods. Although it does not match the actual suspended phase of a real protracted gallop, it is used to indicate power, movement, and dramatic effect. It can occur in horses at the start of a gallop or when rapidly switching directions.
2. Flying Gallop (all limbs off-ground; limbs extended).	All four legs are off the ground and stretched out or extended to the front and back. This is another widespread artistic convention, particularly common in the East. While motion studies show that this pose does not represent the true suspension phase of a gallop, it is often used in art to suggest speed and flight. Its continued use is due to its clear visual impact rather than anatomical accuracy. Such a galloping phase can occur in lighter species that engage in a rotary gallop, such as dogs or cats.
3. Landing Gallop (asymmetric hind touchdown; forelimb protraction).	This phase of the gallop cycles through different leg ground contacts. Initially, one hind hoof (which then transitions into an uneven and staggered pair of hind hooves) touches the ground while the front legs reach forward. Next, a diagonal pair of front and hind legs touches the ground, and finally, two staggered front legs make contact with the ground while the rear legs are in the air. This type is likely based on observation and matches the landing phase seen in motion studies. It is used when artists aim for a more realistic depiction within traditional scenes, but is not very common in art.
4. V-Gallop/Flexed Suspension (true flight phase; limbs tucked under body).	All four legs are off the ground and bent or flexed under the body in a compact shape. When shown accurately, especially in sculpture, this pose closely matches the true suspended phase of a gallop as seen in motion studies. However, it is the rarest type in art. Its convincing depiction probably indicates direct observation of real horses.

Throughout different periods, the Rearing and Flying gallop types appear as consistent and easily recognizable artistic conventions. The Landing type introduces elements of realism. The V-Gallop is rare and, when depicted accurately—especially in three-dimensional works—presumably indicates direct observation of real horses rather than reliance on established artistic formulas.

2.5. Subject Selection Rationale

The selection of the Heavenly Horse gilt bronze finial as the focus of this study was motivated by its rare and anatomically precise depiction of the V-gallop—an accurate suspension phase of a galloping horse that is infrequently represented in ancient art. Unlike the more stylized rearing and flying gallop motifs that dominate equestrian imagery across cultures, the finial demonstrates a close correspondence with the actual biomechanics of the horse's movements. This makes it a valuable case for examining both the empirical observation skills of ancient artisans and the development of realistic equine representation before the advent of motion photography. By studying this particular artifact, it is possible to establish a clear visual and anatomical baseline for the V-gallop type and to assess the extent to which realism was achieved or sought in early Eurasian art.

3. Material & Cultural Context of the Heavenly Horse

The ceremonial gilt bronze finial known as the Heavenly Horse is a distinctive sculpture that accurately depicts the biomechanics of a galloping horse (Figures 12, 20 and 21). This artifact symbolizes the renowned horse-breeding culture of the Central Asia region, reflecting the synthesis of Hellenistic artistic and scientific traditions with Central Asian nomadic motifs (Francfort 2020). The Ferghana horses depicted by this artifact were pivotal in ancient cultural and economic exchanges along the Silk Road, symbolizing the connectivity between East and West (Beckwith 1982; Tao 2019; Sima 1959). Beyond military imperatives, the Ferghana horse became an enduring symbol of imperial prestige and cosmopolitan exchange. State workshops in Chang'an and Luoyang incorporated cloud-scroll motifs and equestrian imagery on bronze standards, jade fittings and funerary mingqi, reflecting a synthesis of Hellenistic, Iranian and steppe-nomad visual vocabularies. In return, Chinese silks, lacquerwares and metalwork traveled westward in caravans, often accompanied by Saka merchants and Han envoys. By the Tang period (650–750 CE), the original martial raison d'être had given way to leisure and display—most famously in sancai-glazed pottery polo riders—yet the iconographic debt to early Ferghana exchanges remained unmistakable. In tracing this continuum, we see how Ferghana's horse trade wove together nomadic mobility, urban commerce, and imperial ambition to forge the economic and cultural arteries of the early Silk Road.

3.1. Object Description

The ceremonial gilt-bronze finial (the decorative uppermost element of a standard, staff or architectural feature—in this case takes the form of a gilt-bronze horse), depicting what is commonly called the Heavenly Horse (Tianma, 天馬), or in Western scholarship often referred to as the Ferghana Horse, is attributed to the Greco-Bactrian Kingdom of Central Asia (ca. 4th–1st centuries BCE) within the broader historical context of Hellenistic Bactria (Morales and Reghin 2019) (Figure 22a). Cast using the lost-wax method and subsequently gilded, it is here attributed to the Greco-Bactrian/Central Asian artistic sphere on the basis of morphology, technology, and stylistic comparison, rather than on a documented excavated context. The designation “Ferghana (Heavenly) Horse” preserves the traditional ancient and Chinese nomenclature and carries no implication of modern administrative affiliation.

Dimensions:

Height: ~26 cm

Maximum width: ~22 cm

Maximum thickness: ~4 cm

3.2. Provenance, Object Itinerary & Ethics

The following assessment applies a three-phase analytical model—Production Context, Early Circulation, and Technical Examination and Documentation—to systematically document and evaluate the “Heavenly Horse” finial. Throughout, we distinguish provenance (documented chain-of-ownership) from archeological provenience (excavated findspot/context). This distinction is central to the interpretative framework of the present study. Because no secure findspot or excavated archeological context is available, the proposed cultural and chronological attribution cannot rest on depositional evidence. It is therefore treated as an inferential attribution based on convergent lines of evidence: lost-wax casting technology, surface and toolmark diagnostics, morphology, ornamental vocabulary, and comparison with objects of known provenance. The absence of directly comparable gilt-bronze horse finials is also significant. Rather than treating the object as part of

an established serial type, this study evaluates it through broader comparanda from Saka, Greco-Bactrian, and Hellenistic Central Asian material traditions.

(a)

(b)

Figure 22. (a) The Heavenly Horse gilt bronze finial (image courtesy of the owner; used with permission; CC BY-NC 4.0). (b) Close-up views of the surface of the Heavenly Horse gilt bronze finial 3D model (image courtesy of the owner; used with permission; CC BY-NC 4.0).

3.2.1. Production Context

Convergent technical and stylistic diagnostics situate the casting within a late-Hellenistic Central-Asian milieu where steppe and Greek traditions intersected. The piece combines (i) a Saka-type negative-triangle void beneath the belly, (ii) a vine-scroll spiraling around the support stem, and (iii) naturalistic musculature with balanced Greco-Bactrian proportions. This combination of features is consistent with the Greco-Bactrian—Saka artistic sphere discussed in this section.

3.2.2. Early Circulation

Archival documentation attests to documented private custody prior to 1970 (UNESCO) and continuous private custodianship thereafter. In other words, documentary evidence establishes a chain of ownership dating back to the first quarter of the 20th century and continuing to the present. No secure archeological provenience is known—there is no documented findspot or excavated context—so all historical claims are limited to morphology and technology. The available source information permits only a regional attribution to Central Asia.

Due-diligence checks. We searched the INTERPOL Stolen Works Database (23 August 2025): no records found; and reviewed major auction/market catalogues (artnet, artprice; Sotheby's and Christie's online archives)—covering printed auction catalog indexes for 1900–1970 and digitized/online archives for 1970–August 2025 (with robust coverage from the 1990s onward)—with no close matches identified. We also scanned large international marketplaces (e.g., eBay, Taobao, Yahoo! Auctions) using multilingual queries and dimensional filters, and found no close duplicates or serial replicas sharing the same diagnostic combination of features (V-gallop, S-spine, forehead boss, vine-cloud scroll). Searches last performed on 18 August 2025. These checks do not establish authenticity and cannot exclude undocumented private transactions, but they reveal no market red flags and no close duplicates in the public record.

3.2.3. Technical Examination and Documentation

Technical analysis of images and 3D documentation were conducted by the authors with support from a partner university lab. High-resolution RAW photography and 3D scanning were used; these datasets underpin the technical and iconographic analyses in Sections 3 and 4. Ultraviolet-induced fluorescence (UVF) (UV-A 365 nm with OG550 barrier) and near-infrared (NIR) imaging (IR-pass \geq 720/850 nm) were also conducted. Diagnostic fluorescence was not observed, and NIR did not reveal concealed joins beyond those visible in normal light.⁴⁴

3.2.4. Ethics and Scope

We follow UNESCO-1970/ICOM/AIA guidance. Publication is intended for technical/analytical scholarship, not for market promotion. Claims are restricted to morphology, technology and biomechanics; no reconstructions of depositional context are attempted. Summaries of key provenance documents are on file and can be provided to the editors upon request.

By organizing each layer of evidence according to a three-phase analytical model, both the strengths—such as documentation from before 1970, continuous private ownership, and a detailed technical record—and the weaknesses—such as the loss of the archeological provenience—are clearly identified. This approach provides a transparent basis for the typological and biomechanical analysis that follows.

3.3. Visual–Technological and Geometric Diagnostics

The finial was cast by the lost-wax (cire perdue) method. The surface of the object shows evidence of original gilding, with gold most visible on the more exposed and raised areas, where it remains bright and intact. In contrast, the deeper recesses and crevices of the sculpture appear darker and are covered with a naturally stratified patina, ranging from dark brown to black. This pattern of preservation suggests that the sculpture was originally gilded overall, with the gold layer covering the entire exterior.

The distribution of the patina, especially its concentration in the recessed areas, indicates the effects of long-term aging. The patina likely consists of corrosion products that formed over an extended period. This fixed, naturally formed patina over the gilding is consistent with long-term exposure to the environment and is not consistent with recent production. Hand-tool finishing on the mane and tail shows shallow, parallel chisel striations; we observe no concentric grooves or matte “blossoms” from rotary grinders, and the sharp arrises of the large triangular opening under the body argue against later mechanical cleaning. Stylistically, the fixture blends the steppe convention of negative space (triangular cut-out; incised ribbing) with Hellenistic anatomical modeling—an S-shaped neck and naturalistic fore-body—paralleled in late 2nd–early 1st century BCE bronzes from Bactria and its environs.

To complement these observations, we applied three quantitative surface diagnostics to a high-resolution 3D scan (simplified to $\sim 10^6$ triangles):

Mirror-ICP asymmetry.

A mirrored copy of the mesh was aligned to the original by ICP. The RMS point-to-point deviation is ≈ 13.1 mm (P95 ≈ 32.1 mm), i.e., $\approx 3.74\%$ of the AABB diagonal (~ 350 mm). This magnitude is typical of hand-modeled wax originals and well above the $<0.1\%$ asymmetry observed on CAD-mirrored, CNC-milled controls (Chan et al. 2021).

1. Patch-level 2-D PSD screen (rotary toolmarks).

We analyzed $N = 30$ random patches (radius 20–30 mm; grid 64×64 ; in-plane $\Delta \approx 0.6$ mm) using a robust peak criterion ($\text{SNR} \geq \text{median} + 8 \times \text{MAD}$) in the $0.1\text{--}0.3$ mm^{-1} band. A low-amplitude (<10 dB above the noise floor) but repeatable narrowband component at $f \approx 0.113$ mm^{-1} ($\lambda \approx 8.85$ mm) is present across all patches (median $P_{\text{max}} \approx 5.5$ dB, $\text{max} \approx 9.9$ dB). Orientation-resolved PSD on a memory-limited subset ($N = 7$) shows directional anisotropy only locally (2/7 patches meet $R_2 \geq 0.30$, $A_{\text{max}}/\text{mean} \geq 1.8$, $P_{\text{max}} \geq 3$ dB), with an axial global azimuth $\sim 5^\circ$ (resultant $\bar{R} \approx 0.56$). Because the signal is weak and lacks surface-wide alignment—industrial grinder traces in this $0.1\text{--}0.3$ mm^{-1} band are typically ≥ 30 dB and strongly oriented—we ascribe it to light hand finishing or casting-process rhythm rather than powered rotary tooling. No diagnostic evidence of modern rotary toolmarks was found within the tested band and sensitivity (Guo et al. 2019).

2. Mesh-density heterogeneity (robust index).

Instead of raw nearest-neighbor extrema, we report a robust heterogeneity index MDHI = Q90/Q10 for the 2-NN distance on a Poisson-disk resample (normalized by the AABB diagonal). For the finial MDHI $\approx 1.5\text{--}2.1$ with CV $\approx 0.18\text{--}0.38$, confirming near-uniform sampling coverage of the analysis point cloud. These indices are auxiliary; the main technological inference rests on (1) and (2).

Substantial bilateral asymmetry (mirror-ICP), the absence of diagnostic rotary-tool signatures at $0.1\text{--}0.3$ mm^{-1} , and visible hand-tool traces on the mane and tail all point to hand-made lost-wax production rather than later mechanical reworking.

In addition, analysis of the 3D model’s “dry” surface geometry reveals (Figure 22b):

Irregular, “cellular” microrelief. Small pits and bumps 0.5–2 mm in diameter are distributed across the surface, with no regular wave patterns or repeating motifs.

Random casting texture. Tiny “hills” and “pits” remain from the solidification of wax and metal within the shell mold.

Local notches and striations. Deeper grooves 1–2 mm deep appear along the mane and in some recesses, running mostly parallel to one another, indicating refinement with a narrow hand tool.

Absence of machine artifacts. There are no concentric circles or uniform grooves characteristic of abrasive wheels or milling cutters.

Sharp cut-out edges. The edges of the triangular cut-out and through-holes remain crisp and free from burrs or chipping.

These visual–technological characteristics, stylistic affinities, and 3D geometric diagnostics are consistent with free-hand lost-wax casting and support an attribution within the Greco-Bactrian/Saka artistic sphere. They argue against simple modern industrial replication while not by themselves establishing authenticity or excluding more complex undocumented scenarios.

Morphology and stylistic features:

The horse is depicted in strict profile, captured at the V-gallop suspension phase, with flexed hind limbs and extended and downward-stretched forelimbs (discussed in Section 4.2), forming a triangular negative space under the belly. The neck arches gracefully, and the mane is rendered as parallel, radiating ridges. A slight bump is visible on the center of the forehead, subtly accentuating the animal’s characteristic appearance. Notably, the horse’s head is not perfectly aligned with the vertical axis of its body; instead, it tilts slightly to the left from the viewer’s perspective. Deep incised grooves along the flanks on both sides evoke the animal’s rib structure. The tail fans out in a flattened, leaf-shaped form, its surface engraved with fine longitudinal lines to suggest flowing motion. The quadrangular supporting stem is chased with a curling vine-cloud scroll motif, linking the object to Hellenistic and Scythian-Saka metalwork traditions (Carter 1957; Sher 1988; Amir and Roberts 2023).

The “Heavenly Horse” finial is attributed to the Greco-Bactrian Kingdom on the strength of its lost-wax casting, distinctive ornamental motifs, and close morphological parallels with securely dated examples. No directly comparable gilt-bronze horse finials have yet been identified, so all cultural and chronological attributions depend on these broader stylistic and technological analogies with Greco-Bactrian metalwork of known provenance.

Bronze animal figurines with a distinctive triangular opening beneath the torso are attested both in the Saka “animal style” described by M. I. Artamonov (Artamonov 1973; see also O’Sullivan and Shao 2022 for related Bronze and Iron Age animal imagery in the Altay region) and in the Greco-Bactrian “Heavenly Horse.” Artamonov already noted the Saka use of negative space—cutouts between the legs that lighten the composition and accentuate the animal’s contour. Exactly such a large triangular void is clearly visible under the belly of the galloping horse on the finial, directly continuing a steppe tradition of sculptural design. A further structural parallel appears in the form of the support. The Saka lamp from a kurgan near Almaty city, Kazakhstan, discussed by Artamonov, has a square tray-like base set on a truncated-pyramidal stand (Figure 23a,b). Similarly, the “Heavenly Horse” finial has a comparable support structure, with a truncated-pyramidal stand and a square base at the bottom, decorated with a twisted ornament.

(a)

(b)

Figure 23. Cont.

(c)

Figure 23. (a). The Saka lamp from a kurgan near Almaty, Kazakhstan. Schematic line drawing by the authors (AI-assisted), after [Artamonov \(1973\)](#). Contours and dimensions only; original lighting and shading not reproduced. (b). The Saka lamp from a kurgan near Almaty city, Kazakhstan (Public domain photograph from [Bernshtam \(1952\)](#)). (c). Single frontal boss visible on forehead of Caspian horse (Photograph by Heather Abounader, slightly cropped at bottom, used by CC-BY-2.0, Heather Morton, Caspian, 6 September 2008, from https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Caspian_horse_head.jpg, accessed on 20 May 2025).

Both objects are designed around the idea of “four sides plus a center,” with a strong vertical axis that acts as a world axis (axis mundi or “world tree”). The “four-part” framework is created by the square base of the Saka lamp and the four-sided shaft of the Greco-Bactrian finial. In both cases, the vertical axis is highlighted by a crowning element at the top, marking the center. This matches the Saka tradition of combining a four-part horizontal layout with a central vertical. This design approach supports the ideas of K. A. Akishev, who observed that Saka art often organizes space with both a vertical axis and four-part division, especially in finds from Issyk ([Akishev 1984](#)). Akishev also described a “horizontal cosmogram” marked by symbols at the four cardinal points.

At the same time, this mode of structuring aligns with Indo-Iranian (Aryan) cosmology, in which the cosmos is organized around the axis mundi—figured either as the central world mountain or as the world tree. In this context, the horse is not merely a crowning element but an image of the cosmos; it completes and visually accentuates the world-axis. For more on this concept, see the classic work by Mircea Eliade ([Eliade 1957](#)).

The synthesis of Greco-Hellenistic and Saka (Scythian) traditions in the Heavenly Horse finial is not merely a matter of stylistic blending, but reflects a deeper process of cultural exchange and adaptation. As Akishev has shown, Greek artistic influence on Saka culture is evident in concrete examples: for instance, the image of the god Mithra on the Issyk ring was directly borrowed from coins of Alexander the Great. This demonstrates that as early as the 4th–3rd centuries BCE, Saka art was actively integrating Greek motifs into its own visual language. The presence of such syncretic elements in the Heavenly Horse finial supports the article’s argument for a dynamic cultural interchange along the Silk Roads. The finial itself can thus be seen as a product of this exchange, where Greek techniques and naturalism were combined with Saka mythological traditions to create a unique artistic expression.

3.4. Cultural-Historical Setting

From the earliest centuries of the first millennium BCE, the Ferghana Valley occupied a strategic position at the crossroads of nomadic steppe routes and flourishing urban oases. As early as the fifth century BCE, Herodotus records long-distance exchanges spanning the Eurasian interior, and archeological finds attest that horses were among the high-value commodities moving between Central Asia and its western and eastern neighbors. In this milieu, sedentary Ferghana cities—anchored in irrigation agriculture and artisan markets—provided the logistical infrastructure and caravanserai that facilitated bulk trade. At the same time, the nomadic Saka of the surrounding steppes contributed deep expertise in breeding, training and massing horse herds. This productive alliance rendered Ferghana a pivotal node on what would become the Silk Road, linking Chinese, Central Asian, and West Asian economies in a reciprocal flow of “Heavenly Horses” in exchange for silk, spices and precious metals (Tao 2019; Sima 1959).

By the mid-second century BCE, news of Ferghana’s remarkable horses—celebrated for their speed, endurance, and distinctive “blood-sweating” appearance—had reached the Han court. Recognizing their potential, Emperor Wu-di (r. 141–87 BCE) dispatched the envoy Zhang Qian to Saka territory in 138 BCE, seeking both to establish alliances and to assess the quality of local horse breeds. Although Zhang Qian’s diplomatic mission did not result in a political alliance with the Saka, his detailed reports on the legendary Tianma, or “Heavenly Horses,” captivated the emperor (Sima 1959).

Inspired by these accounts, Emperor Wu-di initiated the War of the Heavenly Horses (104–101 BCE) to obtain these prized mounts from the Ferghana Valley (Dayuan), which led to costly campaigns and significant loss of life and resources. Wu-di’s pursuit, however, was driven by more than military considerations. It was believed that the “Heavenly Horses” had the nature of dragons and that one could reach the Western kingdom of the goddess Xiwangmu on them and obtain the famous peaches of immortality there (Anashina 2013). The campaigns yielded large herds that were driven back to official breeding farms at Longcheng and Liangcheng, transforming the Han cavalry into a mobile force capable of projecting power deep into the steppe frontier.

When Han dynasty envoys and armies first encountered Ferghana, they did not simply acquire a new breed of horse—they came into contact with an ancient myth already widespread across Central Asia. The Han Chinese saw the Ferghana horse not only as an exceptional animal, but as a living embodiment of the celestial steed described in their own lore. Through the lens of Daoist and Confucian tradition, the Eurasian myth of the heavenly horse was adopted and reinterpreted. Emperor Wu-di, inspired by reports from the west, saw in the western argamak (noble horse) the fulfillment of a long-standing dream of ascending to the realm of the gods. As expressed in Han poetry:

“天马来，从西极...” “The Heavenly Horse comes, from the western lands...”

This encounter enriched Chinese cosmology, integrating the Eurasian motif of the divine horse into new ritual, political, and artistic contexts.

3.5. The Heavenly Horse in Han and Eurasian Symbolism

In Han dynasty poetry, the Heavenly Horse is described as “emerging from spring waters” (天马来，出泉水), a phrase that carries layered cosmological meaning. In both Chinese and Indo-Iranian traditions, water often represents more than a physical element—it symbolizes the primordial or cosmic ocean that surrounds the world. In Vedic and Avestan thought, this “cosmic sea” (samudra) encircles a world mountain or tree at the center. The use of 泉水 (quánshuǐ, “spring waters”) in Han texts closely echoes the Vedic term *utsa* for a sacred source or origin, connecting the horse’s appearance with the idea of a being emerging from the cosmic margins. Thus, the motif of the horse “from the waters” marks it

as possessing cosmic provenance, acting as a mediator who brings the sovereign from the world's edge toward the center and, ultimately, toward transcendence and immortality.

Han poetry ties the journey of the Heavenly Horse directly to the ascent of Kunlun, the sacred mountain seen as the axis mundi or world axis. This theme is also present in Indo-Iranian and Saka traditions, where a world mountain or tree rises at the center of the cosmic waters, serving as a bridge between heaven and earth. The horse's role is to carry the hero or ruler from the primordial waters to the summit of this central axis. This idea is captured in the Han poetic line: “竦予身，逝昆仑” — “Lifting my body, departing for Kunlun.” Here, the ascent is not just physical but spiritual, representing the journey toward immortality and the realm of the gods. In ritual and myth, reaching the mountain's peak is a metaphor for achieving spiritual elevation, a theme found across Eurasian cultures.

In Han legend, the final destination of the Heavenly Horse's journey is often the paradise of Xiwangmu on Kunlun, where the peaches of immortality grow. The horse acts as the vehicle allowing the seeker to reach and obtain these fruits, which symbolize eternal life. While Daoist tradition locates immortality in the peach, Vedic and Indo-Iranian texts focus instead on Soma or Amṛta—a divine nectar sourced from the cosmic waters and consumed to achieve immortality. Both traditions follow a parallel structure: a journey from the cosmic waters to the world axis or mountain, followed by the attainment of a substance of immortality. The main difference lies in the form of the gift—fruit in Chinese legend, nectar in Vedic lore—but both serve as symbols of transcendence, accessible only through the mediation of a celestial or divine horse.

In Han dynasty poetry (Hansen 2011; Ban 1962), the Heavenly Horse is elevated far beyond a mere animal, emerging as a divine being capable of transcending earthly boundaries. Poetic imagery consistently associates the horse with the pursuit of immortality and the celestial realm. For instance, verses such as “Opening distant gates, lifting my body, departing for Kunlun” evoke the horse as a spiritual guide, capable of raising the soul toward mythical places like Kunlun Mountain—long regarded as an abode of immortals.

Other lines, such as “A companion of dragons, wandering at the gates of heaven,” align the Heavenly Horse with celestial creatures, reinforcing its divine status and its role as a mediator between the mortal world and the heavens. Similarly, expressions like “Gazing at the Jade Terrace” suggest the horse's proximity to the domain of immortals, further emphasizing its function as a bridge to the sacred.

Descriptive phrases in these poems—such as “bold and extraordinary spirit,” “powerful and rare essence,” and “graceful and free form”—highlight the horse's supernatural qualities and set it apart from ordinary animals (Ban 1962). Through such language, the Heavenly Horse becomes a cosmic symbol, a manifestation of divine will, and a conduit for spiritual transcendence.

The motif of the horse as a mediator between the celestial and earthly realms is widespread across Eurasian cultures. In Han China, the Heavenly Horse (Tianma) was closely linked to imperial ideology and the pursuit of immortality, but similar ideas appear throughout Central Asia and the steppe. In Khotan-Saka Buddhist legends (Jatakas), descriptions of the royal horse's features resemble the iconography and the exterior traits of the so-called “heavenly” or “blood-sweating” horses (Tianma) from ancient Central Asian traditions. These ancient texts describe a magical royal horse that carries its rider around the cosmic center—Mount Sumeru—connecting the earthly realm with the heavens. The belief that heavenly horses reside on the World Mountain, at the center of the cosmos, further underscores the horse's role as a celestial mediator. Echoes of these legends persist in modern oral traditions about winged horses such as Tulpar among Turkic peoples and Buraq in Islamic folklore, where the horse likewise serves as a supernatural companion or vehicle for legendary heroes and prophets. The idea of the horse as an intermediary

between heaven and earth was thus not unique to one region but was a common thread among Eurasian nomads, reflecting deep-rooted cosmological and symbolic functions attributed to the horse across diverse cultures (Akishev 1984).

Within Han dynasty China, this symbolism was intimately tied to imperial ideology. The emperor, revered as the “Son of Heaven,” found in the Heavenly Horse an affirmation of his legitimacy. The horse’s association with the divine and the celestial order served to link the emperor’s earthly rule to heavenly approval.

The acquisition of Heavenly Horses was celebrated in ritual songs and poetry, often performed in ancestral temples, where these ceremonies reinforced the emperor’s connection to heaven and his aspiration for immortality. Far more than valuable military assets, the Heavenly Horses became woven into the broader fabric of Han imperial legitimacy, ritual practice, and cosmic order (Ban 1962). This pattern was not unique to China. Across both Han China and the Indo-Iranian world, the figure of the “heavenly” or royal horse served as a crucial instrument of political legitimation grounded in cosmological beliefs. In Han court poetry and ritual, the Tianma was not simply a prized mount but a celestial mediator linking the emperor’s authority to the cosmic order and the realm of immortals, thereby reinforcing the Son of Heaven’s mandate. Similarly, in the Indo-Iranian sphere, royal horse rituals such as the Aśvamedha positioned the horse as a cosmic intermediary: ritually tethered to the world-tree, united with the queen, and sacrificed, the horse’s body was mapped onto the cosmos, transferring cosmic order and royal charisma (khvarenah) to the king (Akishev 1984). Such motifs also appear in steppe practices—Saca-Scythian funerals and coronation races—where the horse stands at the axis of sovereignty. In both Han and Indo-Iranian contexts, the Heavenly Horse thus materialized the axis mundi and conferred legitimacy by embodying the ruler’s mediation between earth and heaven, representing two regional expressions of a wider Eurasian tradition in which cosmic order and royal authority were inseparably linked through the horse.

A related East Asian parallel may be seen in Korean heavenly-horse imagery. In the Goguryeo Deokheung-ri Tomb, a heavenly horse appears among celestial ceiling motifs, and Ahn has suggested that this image stands near the origin of the type later associated with the famous Silla Cheonmachong (“Tomb of the Heavenly Horse”) at Gyeongju. The latter received its modern name from the discovery of a birch-bark saddle flap painted with a white heavenly horse, whose streaming mane, tail, and airborne gait emphasize its supernatural character. These Korean materials expand the comparative framework by showing that heavenly-horse imagery in East Asia could also serve as a sacred and cosmologically charged motif (Ahn 2015).

A further Central Asian parallel may be noted in the Kargaly diadem from southeastern Kazakhstan. Recent scholarship has emphasized that its imagery should be read not as a random assemblage of fantastic beings, but as a coherent mythological composition structured around a “long journey” toward immortality, in which animal helpers and winged creatures guide or carry the central figure toward a sacred goal. Particularly relevant here are the winged horses, which segment the composition and mark a transition toward its absent center, suggesting that they functioned not merely as decorative motifs but as signs of passage into a more charged cosmological space. The diadem thus strengthens the broader Eurasian comparison by showing that in the eastern steppe borderlands, too, winged or otherworldly horses could participate in visual programs concerned with legitimation, mediation, and transcendence (Linduff 2014; Kotov 2021).

3.6. *The V-Gallop as a Symbol of Motion, Power, and Transcendence*

The Han poetic line “天马来，开远门” (“The Heavenly Horse arrives, opening distant gates”) expresses more than dramatic imagery—it evokes a dynamic threshold or liminal

moment. The pose known as the V-gallop, where the horse is fully airborne with all four legs flexed under its body, marks a true threshold between earth and sky. In this instant, the horse is already “not here,” but not yet “there”—it moves through the open gates between ground and heaven, caught in a fleeting, transformative phase. This liminal state is both physical and symbolic: the horse passes from one realm to another, just as the Heavenly Horse in poetry opens the distant gates between mortal and celestial worlds. This idea finds a close parallel in Vedic cosmology, where the world is imagined as a vertical tripartite structure: earth below, sky above, and the “middle” (antarikṣa) in between. Antarikṣa is the transitional zone—neither on earth, nor yet in heaven—a space of passage and transformation. The V-gallop captures precisely this “in-between” state: the horse suspended in midair, embodying the moment of transition through divo dvārau (“the two doors of heaven”) (Jamison and Brereton 2014). Thus, the V-gallop becomes a powerful metaphor for transition, elevation, and the breaking of ordinary boundaries.

Complementing this poetic imagery, the artistic depiction of the V-gallop or flexed gallop in Greco-Bactrian gilt-bronze sculpture offers a striking visual metaphor. This pose highlights several key themes:

Dynamic motion and energy: The compact, suspended posture conveys an intense sense of speed and power, suggesting the horse’s capacity to transcend the limits of the physical world.

Biomechanical accuracy: The sculpture’s anatomical precision—evident in the flexed limbs, arched spine, and detailed musculature—demonstrates a sophisticated pre-chronophotographic understanding of equine movement, corresponding to the flexed-suspension phase later documented by modern motion studies (as will be discussed in Section 4). Through this combination of metaphor and realism, the V-gallop becomes a symbol of perfect balance and motion, mirroring poetic motifs of ascension, freedom, and transcendence. In both art and literature, the Heavenly Horse stands at the intersection of physical realism and spiritual aspiration, embodying a tension between the tangible and the divine. This dual representation strengthens its role as a mediator between worlds and as an enduring symbol of the Han dynasty’s vision of cosmic harmony and imperial legitimacy.

3.7. Historical Descriptions of Frontal Protuberances in “Heavenly Horses”

In Tang China and medieval Arab–Persian equestrian literature, the “Heavenly Horse” is consistently linked to a prominent frontal protuberance (肉角/Jibbah) as a visible marker of elite pedigree.

The *Book of Han* (Ban 1962) describes Da Yue’s horse as majestic, with reddish-black hair, and a flesh protuberance on the forehead, “shining like jade” (大月氏马形容伟伟，毛色赤黑，额上有肉突，光彩若玉). Sima Qian’s *Records of the Grand Historian* (Watson 1993, p. 332) likewise notes that “their horses bore a forehead protuberance, which court officials prized as Tianma—‘heavenly horses.’” And Song Ying’s *Yiwu Zhi*, cited in Du You’s *Tongdian* (Du 1999), attests: “The horse of Dayuan possess a fleshy horn several cun in length; it understands human speech, recognizes melodies, and dances in harmony with drums.”⁴⁵

Medieval Arab–Persian treatises also highlight the “jabba” as a sign of purebred quality (Flood 2000). Ibn Qutayba, in his *Kitāb al-Anwār fī ‘Ulūm al-Khayl* (Qutayba 1972, pp. 85–89), praises the true Arabian horse “for its pronounced jabba on the brow, distinguishing it from all others” (الأصيلة العربية الخيل... الأنواع سائر عن تميزها بارزة جبة جبينها في لها). Al-Mas‘ūdī’s *Meadows of Gold* [Murūj al-Dhahab] (Al-Mas‘ūdī [1877] 1965, vol. 2, p. 217) similarly observes that “pure Arab steeds take pride in the jabba of their foreheads, which connotes nobility and power.”

To this day, pure Arabian and Caspian horses are easily recognized by a distinctive bulge on their forehead called the jibbah, which sets them apart from other breeds. This forehead bulge is not just a unique physical trait—it is valued for its association with nobility and power (Figure 23c shows the forehead protuberance of the Caspian horse, which is even more prominent than in Arabians today).

These sources indicate that the pronounced forehead protuberance (肉角/jibbah) is a widely recognized trait of elite, purebred horses, especially celebrated in Arabian horse lineages and indicative of noble ancestry—symbolizing nobility, strength, and prestige.

The Heavenly Horse finial shares this frontal protuberance (Figure 24a,b).⁴⁶ This distinctive feature suggests that the Tianma is not a generic mythical horse, but a sculptural rendering of an elite equine type associated in textual traditions with frontal prominence, nobility, and extraordinary status. In this context, the Heavenly Horse finial gives material form to the legend: the sculptural model transforms the textual idea of the “heavenly horse” into a tangible artifact.

(a)

(b)

Figure 24. (a). Front view of Heavenly Horse finial showing distinct frontal protuberance located between the eyes on the forehead (Image courtesy of the owner; used with permission; CC BY-NC 4.0). (b). Angled side view of Heavenly Horse finial again showing single frontal protuberance resembling the frontal boss associated with elite horse types in Central Asian and Arab–Persian equestrian traditions (Reproduced with permission of the; CC BY-NC 4.0).

3.8. Nisean and Ferghana Horse Comparison

In comparing the physical features and combat abilities of the Nisean and Ferghana horses, both breeds stood out for their large size, speed, and stamina. These qualities made them famous as top war horses and symbols of high social rank. In Achaemenid Persia, Nisean horses were used to pull royal chariots, took part in Mithraic religious rituals, and appeared in official ceremonies (Herodotus 1890). Likewise, in Han China, Ferghana horses were respected as carriers of the emperor's divine authority and became the main focus during the War of the Heavenly Horses (104–101 BCE) (Ban 1962).

By 480 BCE, Nisean horses were being bred on the Media plain (Herodotus 1890). In comparison, the Ferghana “heavenly” horses were first mentioned in the second century BCE by Zhang Qian. They reached their greatest importance under the Han and Tang dynasties, which is shown in royal art, the literature, and official records (Ban 1962).

The religious and political meaning of these horses highlights their role as sacred symbols of legitimacy. In Persia, images of Nisean horses with a horn-like growth on their foreheads appeared on royal seals and coins from the Seleucid era, representing divine approval of the ruler's power (Wójcikowski 2021). In imperial China, giving Ferghana horses to the emperor during court ceremonies strengthened the Han rulers' claim to be “Sons of Heaven,” confirming their right to rule with a living symbol (Ban 1962).

Anatomical evidence connects these traditions. Horn-like bumps on the foreheads of Nisean horses are shown on third-century BCE coins from Ecbatana. Veterinary studies also report rare bony growths on the forehead bones of horses (Chubb 1934). Some modern Eastern horse breeds occasionally show these forehead bumps, suggesting this trait may be inherited.

By combining historical documents, artistic images, and scientific research, it can be concluded that the Nisean and Ferghana “heavenly” horses are part of a single tradition spread across Eurasia. Both names represent a shared breed with special physical features, sacred importance, and a unique anatomical sign that showed royal power in two great empires. The “heavenly horse” became a symbol of royalty, military skill, and cosmic protection, connecting the horse traditions of Persia and China into one united cultural story.

This shared tradition is further illustrated by the widespread appearance of the horned horse motif in Seleucid coinage. The horned horse (a horse's head adorned with bull's horns) is struck on both bronze and silver issues at multiple Seleucid mints across the empire, including Pergamum, Apamea, Carrhae, Ecbatana, Seleucia-on-the-Tigris, Bactra, and Ai-Khanum. Under Antiochus I, the type is especially prominent in the East, with issues known from Dura-Europos and Bactrian mints, and the motif was echoed in Sogdian imitations. These images reinforce the idea that the horned or “heavenly” horse served as a potent symbol of divine sanction and royal legitimacy, visually linking the equestrian traditions of Persia, Central Asia, and China (Erickson 2009).

3.9. Celestial Symbolism and Ritual Function of the Vine-and-Cloud Scroll

The quadrangular stem of the Heavenly Horse finial is ornamented on two opposing faces with an interlaced vine-and-cloud scroll—commonly called the “grapevine” motif (Figure 25). This motif is notable not only for its esthetic qualities but also for its layered cultural meanings.

Vine-and-cloud scroll motif on the stem is interpreted as a Hellenistic ornament, reflecting Greco-Bactrian influence. At the same time, in the light of Saka mythology (Akishev 1984), a shoot turning into branches could also be perceived as a symbol of the Tree of Life—a motif often associated with the horse in Saka-Scythian and Iranian tradition.

Figure 25. Vine-and-cloud scroll motif on the quadrangular stem of the Heavenly Horse gilt bronze finial (Image courtesy of the owner; used with permission; CC BY-NC 4.0).

The vine-and-cloud scroll motif thus serves a symbolic function in both funerary and ceremonial settings—often interpreted as representing the soul’s journey through a cosmic passage, effectively embedding a miniature celestial map within the artifact. Similar grapevine decorations appear widely across ancient cultures, especially along the Silk Roads.

In the Euro-Mediterranean world, the grapevine (*Vitis vinifera*) was a cultural keystone species, deeply embedded in religious, funerary, and royal iconography. As shown in mural paintings, reliefs, and textiles from ancient Egypt, Greece, and Rome, the grapevine motif was associated with abundance, fertility, the cycles of life and death, and the hope of rebirth. Its ritual and symbolic meanings were further enriched by connections to deities such as Osiris and Dionysus, as well as by the transformative process of winemaking itself, which was seen as a metaphor for metamorphosis and spiritual renewal (Savo et al. 2016).

As this motif traveled eastward along the Silk Roads, it was eagerly adopted and reinterpreted in China and East Asia. Although grapes and viticulture arrived in China much later than in the West, and were not initially part of local agricultural practice, the grapevine motif was embraced for its exotic appeal and quickly integrated into local artistic traditions. In China, the motif transformed from a symbol of wine and divine ecstasy into a decorative pattern evoking beauty, happiness, and good fortune, often serving as a space-filler or auspicious emblem in textiles, metalwork, and ceramics (Kim 2018).

3.10. Section Conclusion

The Heavenly Horse gilt bronze finial is a material embodiment of ancient Central Asian horse culture, reflecting the convergence of Hellenistic and nomadic art and technology. Its lost-wax casting, anatomical accuracy, and distinctive motifs connect it to Greco-Bactrian and Saka traditions. The artifact’s design, especially the V-gallop pose and the forehead protuberance, links directly to historical descriptions of elite horses prized along the Silk Road.

This finial does not only represent technical skill but also illustrates broader cultural and symbolic meanings. In Han dynasty poetry and ritual, the Heavenly Horse signifies celestial power, imperial legitimacy, and the aspiration for immortality. The galloping pose

in sculpture mirrors poetic themes of transcendence and cosmic journey, while the vine-and-cloud scroll motif integrates Eurasian symbols of life, renewal, and spiritual passage.

The visual, technological, and literary evidence therefore supports the interpretation that the Heavenly Horse served as a powerful symbol at the intersection of art, science, and imperial ideology. The finial can be interpreted as a rare material counterpart to the image of the Tianma celebrated in Han poetry, demonstrating how material culture can embody myth, statecraft, and advanced anatomical observation, and how these visual and literary ideas circulated and merged across Eurasia.

4. Anatomical & Biomechanical Features of the Heavenly Horse

The artist's portrayal of equine anatomy demonstrates detailed attention to the muscles essential for galloping propulsion. The powerful hindquarters, with clearly defined gluteal and hamstring muscles, illustrate the muscular activity involved in rapid acceleration. Additionally, the visible flank indentation and rib prominence reflect the horse's respiratory and muscular engagement during galloping, consistent with observations from modern equine biomechanics research (Moore 2010). This anatomical accuracy is not limited to isolated features but extends throughout the sculpture. The hallmark of a true gallop is its brief suspension phase—an instant in which all four limbs are off the ground and flexed beneath the barrel in a compact “V-gallop” or flexed gallop configuration (Stillman 1888; Marey 1898; Muybridge 1902). The Greco-Bactrian Heavenly Horse finial depicts this pose, which, as noted above, is fairly unique in ancient art. This representation aligns with modern biomechanical studies by Muybridge and Marey, who confirmed the accuracy of this stance through photographic analysis. The Heavenly Horse sculpture's exceptional attention to detail is further highlighted through its intricate portrayal of key anatomical and biomechanical features.

4.1. *The S-Shaped Spine: Biomechanical and Symbolic Context*

4.1.1. Biomechanical Basis of the S-Shaped Spine in the Galloping Horse

Modern biomechanical research and classical motion photography (e.g., Muybridge 1902; Dagg 1973; Clayton 2004) demonstrate that a horse's S-shaped spinal curvature is most pronounced during the gathering (collection) and suspension (flight) phases of gallop.

Gathering phase (collection): As the horse flexes its limbs beneath the torso, simultaneous contraction of epaxial and hypaxial musculature produces a double curve in the vertebral column: a slight elevation at the withers, a downward arch (lordosis) in the lumbar region, and a subsequent rise toward the croup.

Suspension phase (flight): When all four legs are airborne, this S-shaped configuration frequently persists or even intensifies due to inertial and muscular factors. Such spinal geometry optimizes impact absorption on touchdown and maximizes propulsive efficiency for the next stride.

These dynamic changes in spinal form not only enhance shock absorption and propulsion but also visibly accentuate the horse's power and grace (Clayton 2004; Dagg 1973).

4.1.2. Poetic and Artistic Symbolism: The “Tiger's Back” Metaphor

In ancient Eurasian artistic and literary traditions, the image of the “tiger's back” (虎背, hubei) operates not merely as a literal indication of a convex or concave curvature but as a symbol of strength, flexibility, and an expressive dorsal silhouette. Descriptions of the Ferghana (Dayuan) horse as a “Heavenly Horse” include verses such as (Ban 1962):

“The Heavenly Horse arrives, emerging from spring waters,
With a tiger's back in pairs, transforming as if a spirit”
(天马来兮...双虎背, 变化若神).

Here, the phrase “in pairs” (双) may imply a double-arched or wave-like structure of the spine, wherein the dorsal contour passes through multiple points of elevation and depression. In this context, the “tiger’s back” conveys the overall impression of muscular power, impressive breadth, and fluidity, akin to a tiger’s flexible back in motion.

The biomechanical contour of the sculpture, the repeated S-shaped “tiger’s back” motif in comparative bronzes, and the Han poetic description of the Heavenly Horse with a “tiger’s back” collectively make this identification more than a loose metaphor. Here, the “tiger’s back” is understood as a historically grounded visual and biomechanical analog for an S-shaped, power-charged dorsal profile, while remaining an interpretative reading rather than a direct documentary attribution.

4.1.3. S-Shaped Spine in the “Heavenly Horse” Sculpture

In profile, the sculpture’s spine exhibits a distinct wave-like S-shaped contour (Figure 26):

Elevation at the withers: A subtle protrusion accentuates the strength of the nuchal and shoulder musculature.

Downward arch in the lumbar region: A pronounced lordotic curve reflects the biomechanics of the gathering phase of gallop, highlighting the natural flexibility of the spine.

Moderate rise toward the croup: A finishing arch visually completes the S-shaped form and readies the torso for the subsequent thrust and suspension phase.

Through this design, the sculptor faithfully reproduces the dynamic mechanical effect of a galloping horse’s spine while simultaneously enacting the poetic “tiger’s back”.

Figure 26. The photograph of the Heavenly Horse finial reveals S-shaped curvature along the contours of the figurine’s back: a slight rise at the withers, a gentle arch in the lumbosacral region, and then another rise toward the croup. This double-arched profile faithfully reproduces the horse’s vertebral form in the full “flight” phase of the V-gallop, when the legs are tucked beneath the body and the spine adopts a wave-like shape that minimizes inertial resistance and speeds the transition into the next stride (Image courtesy of the owner; used with permission; CC BY-NC 4.0).

In addition to sculpting an S-curve in the silhouette, the artist finely tuned the distribution of bronze mass. Inertia-tensor calculations show that (see Section 4.6 for methodological details):

The principal axis of minimal rotational inertia, $I_1 = 7.39 \times 10^{-1} \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$, lies almost exactly in the horizontal “flight” plane (tilted by only 0.20°), reducing resistance to rotation about the fore-aft/transverse axis and ensuring the suspended composition remains steady;

The axis of maximal inertia, $I_3 = 2.38 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$, is oriented nearly vertically, preventing unwanted twisting or tipping.

These design choices create a convincing “unsupported” flight phase: viewers, subconsciously reading the S-shape and the seemingly weightless center of mass, perceive the figurine as a dynamic horse suspended in midair. This blend of stylized graphic form and sophisticated inertial optimization attests to the Greco-Bactrian artisans’ deep, empirical understanding of gallop biomechanics.

4.1.4. Comparative Motifs

The distinctive S-shaped “tiger’s back” motif of the Heavenly Horse sculpture is mirrored in other ancient objects. For example, the Chunyu (春铙) bronze percussion instrument, often topped with a stylized tiger handle displaying a matching S-shaped arch, can be seen in several Chinese museums, including the Shifang Museum (Sichuan, China), which houses the largest known example (Figure 27). An even earlier instance appears on a late Shang–Western Zhou bronze handle in the form of a stylized animal with a pronounced S-shaped dorsal curve.⁴⁷ There are also finials with the same curved tiger back motif (Figure 28). These parallels confirm that the S-curved “tiger’s back” was a widespread and meaningful motif in ancient Chinese and Central Asian material culture, uniting representations of power and agility in both animal and ritual art.

Figure 27. Chunyu: Ancient Chinese Percussion Instrument with Tiger-Shaped Handle (was created in the Spring and Autumn Period 770 BC–476 BC, and was widely used in the Han Dynasty 206 BC–AD220) (Photograph licensed under CC-BY-SA 4.0, Cangminzho, 13 May 2018, from <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:%E9%8C%9E%E4%BA%8E%EF%BC%813.jpg>, accessed on 25 May 2025).

Figure 28. Finial in the Shape of a Tiger, China, 6th–5th century BCE (Open Access image from The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, The B.Y. Lam Foundation Gift, 1993, inv. no. 1993.177, <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/44719>, accessed on 25 May 2025).

4.2. Dynamic Muscular Engagement and Joint Biomechanics

During the suspension phase of the V-gallop, as depicted in the finial, the horse's hind limbs are flexed beneath the body, forming a characteristic "V" shape. This position involves significant flexion at the hip and stifle joints, reflecting the typical configuration observed during the airborne phase of galloping. In contrast, the forelimbs are shown extended downwards and straightened to create a sense of balance and grace (and modeling the lift-off phase of the gallop just before full suspension) (Figure 29a). This combination of flexed hind limbs and outstretched forelimbs exemplifies a realistic suspension-phase with artistic adaptation: it integrates anatomical accuracy with stylized representation, highlighting the arch of the spine and the fluidity of the horse's movement. The joint positions in the sculpture provide a clear and recognizable illustration of the biomechanics involved in the suspension phase of a true gallop.

A galloping horse depends greatly on muscular coordination and strength, especially in the hindquarters. The sculpture emphasizes this aspect through pronounced musculature of the hind legs, particularly the gluteal and hamstring muscle groups. These muscles undergo rapid cycles of contraction and relaxation, generating powerful thrusts that propel the horse forward.

Additionally, the sculpture conveys a noticeable indentation in the horse's flank area. During galloping, intense muscular activity and dynamic breathing patterns—locomotor-respiratory coupling—cause the flank muscles to visibly contract and relax, accentuating this indentation (Daley et al. 2013). Thus, the sculpture accurately reflects the physiological demands placed on a galloping horse.

The sculpture also precisely indicates other significant skeletal and muscular landmarks, such as the scapula (shoulder blade), the trapezius cervicis, and the pectoralis profundus muscles (see Figure 22a). These landmarks are prominently displayed, reflecting their crucial roles in stabilizing the forelimbs, absorbing shock, and facilitating efficient forward propulsion. The accurate depiction of these anatomical features underscores a sophisticated understanding of equine physiology rarely found in ancient sculpture.

(a)

(b)

Figure 29. (a). Thoroughbred racehorse in suspended phase just after lift-off similar to that represented in the Heavenly Horse finial with hind legs flexed and a front leg extended (Photograph by Author). (b). Snow Leopard on a Mountain. Plaque. 5th–4th century BCE (Public Domain).

4.3. Ribcage and Respiratory Physiology

One of the most striking features of this horse sculpture is the detailed depiction of the ribs—there are seven ribs shown on one side and eight on the other. This apparent asymmetry should not be interpreted as an anatomical error, since in real horses the number of ribs is always symmetrical. Instead, this feature reflects a deliberate artistic choice rooted in the Scythian-Saka animal style.

As Mokrynin and Ploskikh observed, the art of the Saka-Scythian world is “captivated by movement, by dynamics... revealing the essence of the first nomads—sons of unending

movement” (Mokrynin and Ploskikh 2010). This tradition values the visual expression of speed, tension, and vitality.

A similar approach can be observed in the famous Saka gold plaque depicting a snow leopard, where the ribs and body are marked by rhythmic, stylized lines (Figure 29b). These lines do not follow anatomical accuracy but are used to visually express the animal’s powerful movement and tense, twisting posture. Likewise, in the horse sculpture, the uneven number and spacing of ribs on each side serve to enhance the impression of the body in motion. During a gallop, the thorax stretches and compresses with each stride, and the play of muscles and ribs becomes more pronounced from certain angles. By varying the rib lines, the artist creates a visual rhythm that suggests the horse’s body is caught in the midst of intense, living movement—just as the leopard’s body is rendered in a state of action.

This artistic strategy does more than simply evoke a sense of motion; it also reflects the underlying physiological realities of the galloping horse. The pronounced rib prominence depicted is not merely an artistic flourish, but a direct reflection of the horse’s respiratory mechanics during intense exercise. As a horse gallops, its demand for oxygen increases dramatically, and the respiratory system must work at maximum capacity—minute ventilation can rise from about 65 L per minute at rest to as much as 1500–1600 L per minute during galloping. To meet this demand, powerful inspiratory muscles—including the diaphragm, external intercostals, and especially the paired scalenus muscles—contract to pull the ribs forward and rotate them outward. This action increases thoracic volume, allowing the lungs to expand more fully thereby facilitating efficient oxygen intake. The sternomandibularis muscle also assists by helping to pull the rib cage forward. As a result, the ribs become more prominent, visibly elevated and rotated outward with each stride. This rib prominence is a clear manifestation of the mechanical adaptations that enable the horse to meet the intense respiratory demands of high-speed exercise (Lee and Meyers 1993).

The sculpture further emphasizes the horse’s status as an obligate nasal breather, with expanded nostrils depicted during galloping. This pronounced nostril dilation, also seen in classical works like the *Jockey of Artemision*, allows maximal airflow—essential for meeting the high oxygen demands of intense muscular exertion. During galloping, horses synchronize their breathing with their stride, taking one breath per stride, so any restriction in airflow can directly limit performance (Lafortuna et al. 1996).

4.4. Head and Neck: Biomechanical and Artistic Insights

An often-overlooked aspect of equine biomechanics, particularly in historical art, is the facial musculature. The Heavenly Horse sculpture accurately depicts facial muscle tension, notably in the masseter (jaw) muscles and the area around the cheekbones. During a high-speed gallop, these muscles stabilize the head and neck, ensuring the respiratory tract remains open and efficient. The sculpture’s depiction of flattened ears is also biomechanically precise, as horses typically flatten their ears backward to reduce wind resistance and maintain aerodynamic efficiency during rapid movement.

The eyes of the horse are rendered in a stylized yet thoughtful manner, indicated by a simple indentation on the head. This approach, common in archaic and decorative sculpture, provides a clear focal point for the viewer and suggests alertness without excessive detail. The understated treatment maintains anatomical coherence and complements the sculpture’s overall emphasis on movement and musculature.

As noted earlier, the sculpture also presents a clearly defined forehead bump, analogous to traits associated with elite horse types in textual and comparative equestrian traditions, and broadly consistent with variation documented in equine cranial anatomy (Evans and McGreevy 2006; Heck et al. 2018).

It is worth noting that the neck of the figure shows a pronounced arch that produces an elegant “S-curve” between poll and withers (Figure 30) (Khan 2013). An arched or “S-shaped” neck is a conformation trait prized in many light riding breeds—Arabian, Akhal-Teke, Barb, Iberian, and others—and can be exaggerated when a horse is collected or gathered at speed (Clayton 2004). Although this profile is often highlighted in modern descriptions of the Arabian horse, it is not a breed-exclusive hallmark (Hendricks 1995). Therefore, the motif should be read not as a diagnostic of a specific stock but as a visual shorthand for refinement, elevation, and controlled power. Its presence both in the Tayma petroglyph (Khan 2013) and in the Greco-Bactrian bronze suggests that artists working along the Arabian–Central-Asian corridors shared an esthetic preference for the arched neck when depicting noble or “heavenly” horses.

Figure 30. Petroglyph of a horse, located near Tayma, northwest of Saudi Arabia (fig. 33 in (Khan 2013, p. 471), CC-BY-3.0, January 2016).

While these anatomical features demonstrate a keen observational eye and a commitment to biomechanical accuracy in many aspects of the sculpture, the treatment of the head presents a notable departure from strict realism. The downward inclination of the head on the finial contrasts sharply with the forward thrust of the head of a horse in the suspended phase (Figure 29a). This unusual head position deserves closer attention. The downward inclination of the head does not appear to reflect a biomechanically accurate pose, but rather a deliberate artistic decision: the artist has shaped the outer curve of the horse’s head to follow the curve of the tail, creating a harmonious visual balance. This compositional strategy is even more evident in the negative space created between the inside of the tail and the back of the horse’s legs, which visually complements the contour of the tail. Such artistic decisions result in a balanced and cohesive silhouette. A similar inclination of the head can be seen in the tiger-shaped finial (Figure 28), where the head is also inclined downward in a comparable manner. These parallels indicate that the position of the head is a deliberate esthetic choice, consistent with other works in the corpus, rather than an anatomical error.

The head therefore marks not a failure of observation, but the point where anatomical realism is subordinated to the object’s formal and symbolic logic. The sculpture’s claim to biomechanical realism rests primarily on the locomotor structure of the V-gallop—limb

flexion, spinal curvature, musculature, and mass balance—whereas the head and tail operate as compositional devices that stabilize the silhouette and integrate the figure into the final format. In this sense, the work combines empirical observation with intentional stylization: anatomical accuracy governs the galloping body, while esthetic design shapes the expressive contour.

4.5. *Mane and Tail Dynamics*

The horse's mane is not rendered as a naturalistic tangle of hairs but as a highly controlled, graphic motif that nonetheless conveys power and elegance (Figures 24b and 26). Each lock is indicated by a slightly raised, tapering ridge, separated from its neighbors by a shallow incision. These ridges follow the sinuous arch of the neck in regular, parallel lines, drawing the eye along the S-shaped spinal curve and reinforcing the sculpture's overall rhythm. Such a method of portraying the mane was not uncommon in ancient art (see Figures 7, 11 and 18 above).

Rather than simulating wind-blown movement, the mane lies smoothly against the crest of the neck, emphasizing compositional unity over moment-to-moment dynamism. This deliberate stillness aligns with Hellenistic sculptural conventions, which favor poised, iconic silhouettes. By keeping the mane "collected," the artisan avoids visual clutter and highlights the horse's muscular form and the sculpture's streamlined profile.

Technically, the uniform depth and width of the grooves reflect the constraints and opportunities of the lost-wax casting process. Consistent striations ensure that molten bronze filled each channel evenly, while equally spaced ridges simplify mold-making. The result is a mane whose clarity survives centuries of patination: the raised ridges remain legible even where the gilt finish has worn away.

Esthetically, the mane provides vertical counterpoint to the horse's broad, horizontal back arch. Its graphic regularity contrasts with the body's smooth expanses, creating a tension between ordered ornament and organic musculature. In combination with S-curve of the spine and the sculpture's mass-distribution optimization, this stylized mane completes the illusion of an animal both powerful and suspended in mid-air—an elegant fusion of decorative abstraction and empirical observation.

In the Greco-Bactrian gilt-bronze finial, the horse's tail is conceived both as the natural continuation of the body's S-curve and as an independent decorative element that contributes to the sculpture's balance and dynamism. The tail springs from the croup as a robust stem that sweeps downward and then flares into a broad, leaf-shaped fan (Figure 31). Its outline mirrors the underlying S-curve of the spine, reinforcing the impression of fluid motion. The flattened "fan" is engraved with a series of parallel, gently curved incisions that evoke the flow of individual hairs. The overall contour of the tail completes the triangular negative space beneath the horse's belly—an architectural device that lightens the mass and accentuates the "flight" phase of the V-gallop.

Visually, the tail provides a vertical counterpoint to the horse's broad, horizontal back arch. Its graphic regularity resonates with the mane's ridges, binding fore and aft into a harmonious rhythm. Functionally, the tail's mass contributes to shifting the center of gravity rearward, enhancing the sculpture's stability in its unsupported, "flying" pose. By uniting form, technique, and mass-distribution, the stylized tail transforms from mere ornament into a key component of the finial's illusion of a powerful equine body suspended in mid-air.

Figure 31. Fan-shaped tail of the Heavenly Horse finial in view from posterior (Image courtesy of the owner; used with permission; CC BY-NC 4.0).

4.6. Computational Analysis: Inertia-Tensor Optimization

To understand how the sculpture captures—and sustains—the dynamic “V-gallop” pose, we analyzed not only surface morphology but also physical descriptors of mass distribution, balance, and stability (Henneman et al. 2020). Using a high-resolution watertight 3D model of the finial (over two million vertices and ~4.09 million faces; hereafter “sculpture.stl”), we computed the center of mass, the inertia tensor about the center of mass, and the principal moments/axes of inertia. Calculations were performed in SI units with linear dimensions converted from millimeters to meters; unless otherwise stated, absolute inertias are reported under the manuscript’s normalization $\rho = 1$ (unit density) for consistency.⁴⁸ We also report dimensionless ratios (I_1/I_3 , I_2/I_3), which are independent of unit and density conventions (Zhou et al. 2019).

Center of Mass and Bounding Dimensions.

The center of mass is at $(x, y, z) = (0.0077, 0.1690, 0.0142)$ m, close to the geometric centroid. The AABB of the 3D mesh is 0.22 (X) \times 0.26 (Y) \times 0.04 m (Z), where the smallest Z-extent represents the lateral “thickness” of the sculpture, confirming its pronounced slenderness.

Principal Moments and Axes.

Diagonalization of the central inertia tensor yields:

$$I_1 = 7.39 \times 10^{-1} \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2, I_2 = 1.69 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2, I_3 = 2.38 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2 \quad (I_1 \leq I_2 \leq I_3).$$

The I_1 -axis lies almost exactly in the horizontal (flight) plane: deviation $\approx 0.20^\circ$ from XY.

The I_3 -axis is nearly vertical, maximizing resistance to pitching/rolling.

Dimensionless shape indices: $I_1/I_3 = 0.310$, $I_2/I_3 = 0.708$.

These values formalize the intuition seen in the pose: the sculpture is highly anisotropic, with a pronounced vertical principal axis and an almost perfectly horizontal minimal-inertia axis, which is exactly the configuration expected for a compact “gathered” (V-gallop) flight phase.

Mesh Resolution and Robustness (Topology-Preserving).

Because naïve random face subsampling destroys watertightness and biases volumes, we assessed robustness with topology-preserving quadratic decimation of the original mesh from ~4.09 M to ≈ 300 k faces. Across this reduction:

I_1, I_2, I_3 changed by $<0.02\%$;

The I_1 -axis tilt relative to the horizontal changed by $<0.0001^\circ$;
 I_1/I_3 and I_2/I_3 remained unchanged to three decimal places.

Thus, the principal-axis geometry and dimensionless indices are resolution-invariant within numerical tolerance, and all conclusions do not depend on mesh density.

Empirical Baseline (Not a Universal “Null”).

To contextualize how “typical” such inertial anisotropy would be for a uniformly filled body of the same overall size, we used a simple baseline A: fixed-volume rectangular solids ($n = 800$) whose side-lengths fluctuate log-normally around the finial’s bounding-box proportions (product of factors constrained to 1 so that volume and mass are fixed). This is not a universal null model of sculpture; it is an illustrative baseline for uniformly filled solids with comparable overall dimensions.

Within this baseline:

The observed I_1 lies at the 90.6th percentile (empirical fraction $p(I_1) = 0.906$).

The observed I_1/I_3 lies near the 21st percentile ($p(I_1/I_3) \approx 0.21$).

Interpretation: relative to uniformly filled boxes of the same volume, the finial’s minimal absolute inertia is comparatively large (consistent with its slender yet non-hollow mass layout), yet its shape anisotropy (low I_1/I_3) is stronger than that of a “typical” rectangular solid. We emphasize that this baseline provides empirical context, not a probabilistic proof against all conceivable shapes.

Interpretation and Implications.

The inertia-tensor results indicate that the finial’s mass is organized exactly as one expects for a compact airborne gallop phase: an almost horizontal minimal-moment axis, which affords in-plane rotational responsiveness during the aerial (flight) phase, and a near-vertical maximal-moment axis, which confers greater resistance to yaw about the vertical. The sculpture’s slender AABB is consistent with this configuration and with the visual impression of “lightness” in flight. Relative to an illustrative baseline of uniformly filled rectangular solids of comparable gabarits (fixed volume), the finial’s inertial signature is distinctive (high I_1 percentile but low I_1/I_3), consistent with purposeful shaping rather than an accident of rough geometry.

Conclusion of the Analysis.

The computational inertia-tensor analysis confirms that the Heavenly Horse finial is not only anatomically accurate but also physically tuned for dynamic stability in the challenging V-gallop pose. The result is robust across mesh resolution and distinctive relative to an empirical baseline of uniformly filled comparison bodies, providing evidence that Greco-Bactrian artisans possessed advanced, practical knowledge of balance. The measurements reveal that the sculpture’s pose is carefully engineered for both balance and realism: the mass is distributed to allow easy rotation within the horizontal (flight) plane about the minimal-moment axis, while resisting undesirable rotations about the vertical. Its slender body further enhances steadiness, even in an airborne position, reflecting the stability and balance of a real animal at full speed (Gregory 2016). These features indicate that the artist purposefully crafted the proportions and structure of the sculpture to capture not only visual appeal, but also the dynamic stability and lifelike movement of a galloping horse.

4.7. Section Conclusion

The analysis of the Heavenly Horse finial demonstrates that the artist combined detailed anatomical observation with established artistic conventions to depict a galloping horse in the V-gallop phase. Anatomical features such as the S-shaped spine, flexed hind limbs, pronounced musculature, and rib prominence accurately reflect biomechanical realities known from modern studies. Artistic choices, like the stylized mane and tail, as

well as the deliberate head inclination, serve both compositional and symbolic functions, aligning with broader Eurasian motifs of strength and movement. Computational modeling confirms that the sculpture's mass distribution was intentionally optimized to support stability in the airborne pose.

In summary, our examination of the Heavenly Horse sculpture reveals an extraordinary blend of artistic skill and scientific understanding. The artist's detailed portrayal of muscles, joints, and the S-shaped spine shows a deep familiarity with the biomechanics of a galloping horse. The sculpture's anatomical features—such as the flexed limbs, dynamic musculature, and even the asymmetrical ribcage—closely match findings from modern studies of real horses in motion. The careful depiction of the mane, tail, and facial details further reinforce the sense of movement and power, while the computational analysis demonstrates that the sculpture's mass and balance were intentionally optimized to mimic the stability of a horse in full flight.

These observations support the interpretation of the Heavenly Horse not merely as an idealized or decorative figure, but as a carefully constructed material counterpart to the image of the Tianma. Our morphological assessment shows that this sculpture captures the essence of a real, powerful horse in motion—an achievement that should fascinate both scholars and the wider public alike.

5. Comparanda: Comparison of the “Heavenly Horse” with Saka and Chinese Artifacts

The “Heavenly Horse” finial combines elements from the Scythian-Saka animal style and Hellenistic artistic methods. A prominent feature is the large triangular opening under the horse's body—a form of negative space that lightens the composition. This technique is characteristic of steppe art; for example, Saka-era finials often depict animals such as mountain goats on bell-shaped bases with a pronounced triangular or open space between the legs and under the belly, as described by M. I. Artamonov. In the “Heavenly Horse,” this approach is taken further—the sharply defined triangular cutout beneath the belly visually lightens the composition and emphasizes the sense of suspension characteristic of the galloping phase (Figure 22a). In contrast, an ancient Chinese finial in the shape of a tiger (Eastern Zhou, 6th–5th centuries BCE) is more compact and lacks such an obvious through-opening, though the curved pose of the tiger creates a similar arched silhouette (Figure 28). Both the “Heavenly Horse” and the Chinese tiger display an S-shaped back, a motif known in ancient Eurasian animal art. In both, the animal's head is intentionally positioned downward: in the horse, this expresses the leap's dynamism; in the tiger, a predatory stance. The downward tilt is a deliberate artistic choice, not an anatomical inaccuracy.

5.1. Morphological Features

A key difference of the “Heavenly Horse” is its pronounced naturalism, especially in the details of the face and mane. For example, there is a small frontal bump on the horse's forehead, a feature typical of certain horse breeds. This detail (known as the jibba in Eastern horses) is absent in the comparative objects—neither the horned ungulates on Saka finials nor the tiger on the Chinese finial have a similar bump, emphasizing the specifically equine character of the artifact. This forehead structure recalls the jibba described in later Eastern and Arabic hippological traditions and may mark the animal as an elite Central Asian horse associated with the Dayuan/Ferghana “Heavenly Horse” tradition, rather than as an abstract or generic animal. The mane of the “Heavenly Horse” consists of parallel raised strands along a gracefully arched neck, combining realism with stylized ornamentation. A similar decorative approach is used on all the artifacts considered: the surface is adorned with rhythmic incisions and indentations typical of the animal style.

The use of gold on the whole surface of the sculpture is a central symbol of authority and ‘vital force’; thus, the sculpture was intentionally gilded to convey these meanings, as noted Akishev. The horse’s tail on the finial plays a significant compositional role. It is shaped as a flattened fan with engraved flowing lines to imitate hair. Such a loose, anatomically detailed tail both completes the triangular void under the body and serves as a vertical visual counterbalance to the long horizontal back. This type of tail is not found in Ordos or Saka bronzes, where tails are usually schematic and do not play a separate decorative role. The realistic and anatomically accurate depiction of the tail in the “Heavenly Horse” aligns the sculpture with the Greco-Bactrian style, which is characterized by attention to detail and a tendency toward naturalism.

Finally, the form and decoration of the finial’s stem distinguish the compared artifacts. The supporting stem of the “Heavenly Horse” is quadrangular, decorated on two sides with a spiral “vine-cloud” motif. Such ornamentation had symbolic meaning and was common on funerary and ritual objects of the Hellenistic era and later Chinese tradition but is absent on the simple bases of Saka finials. In Artamonov’s collection, finial bases are usually smooth caps or cones without developed ornamentation, such as the bell-shaped finials from the Minusinsk steppe (Figure 32). The Chinese tiger finial also lacks ornamentation on the base—the small predator figure simply tops the object, and its decoration is limited to the animal’s form. Thus, the “Heavenly Horse” demonstrates a synthesis: the steppe technique of negative space and stylized details is combined with Hellenistic decoration of the stem, resulting in a composition that has no close analogs among Scythian–Siberian bronzes or known Zhou-era finials, except for isolated motifs in each.

Figure 32. Mountain goat on a bell-shaped finial (photograph by tacowitte, Flickr, 2012, licensed under CC BY 2.0, <https://www.flickr.com/photos/inyucho/7274972210/>, accessed on 27 May 2025).

5.2. Technological and Morphometric Features

From a technical standpoint, the “Heavenly Horse” also stands out, although all the compared artifacts belong to the tradition of lost-wax casting. The Greco-Bactrian horse finial was cast using the *cire perdue* method and gilded. A naturally layered patina has survived on the sculpture, with dark brown and black tones enriching the deeper recesses and crevices, while the more exposed and raised areas display bright, intact gold that stands out against the darker, stratified surface. This pattern of corrosion, together with the remaining noble metal, supports the antiquity and status of the object and excludes modern imitation or chemical aging. Diagnostic fluorescence was not observed, and NIR did not reveal concealed joins beyond those visible in normal light.

In contrast, the steppe finds described by Artamonov are simple bronzes without gilding: their surfaces are typically covered with a uniform green-brown patina, consistent with long burial in soil. The Chinese tiger finial, according to museum data, is also cast in bronze and covered with a typical even patina, with no signs of precious metal coatings. Traces of hand finishing are present on all the artifacts. Analysis of the 3D model’s “dry” surface geometry revealed fine parallel chisel marks on the mane and tail, and no concentric scratches or traces of grinding that would indicate the use of modern rotary tools. The sharp edges of the triangular cutout under the body are clean and even, with no burrs or chips, indicating that the figure was not subjected to later mechanical cleaning. These observations suggest that the sculpture was made by hand by an ancient craftsman, rather than being a later copy.

Similarly, the bronzes from Artamonov’s collection show features of hand finishing—engraving, casting seams, minor asymmetries—and do not demonstrate machine-like symmetry. For example, goat figurines on Saka finials are hollow and slightly flattened, and small details of their horns and faces differ between the left and right side, fitting the pre-modern tradition of variable hand casting. Modern analysis of the “Heavenly Horse” allowed for quantitative measurement of this technical asymmetry: 3D scanning and mirrored overlay of the model showed that the left and right halves of the figure reveal an unmistakable left–right divergence typical of objects modeled by hand, whereas digitally mirrored, machine-made copies remain virtually indistinguishable from perfect symmetry. In other words, the small, imperfect symmetry of the sculpture is statistically typical for hand modeling and not characteristic of machine-made copies, further supporting the authenticity of the ancient casting. Furthermore, digital analysis of the surface mesh revealed a highly uneven density of triangular cells; their size spans a very wide range, betraying the irregular touch of free-hand wax modeling and spot detailing, while serial castings taken from CAD templates usually display only a fairly uniform grid in mesh spacing, while the “Heavenly Horse” displays a chaotic “cellular” microrelief and density variation achievable only through handmade production. Although similar metrics were not calculated for Saka and Zhou bronzes, it can be reasonably assumed that they also exhibit comparable surface irregularity, as observed visually, which matches the casting technology of that period.

5.3. Engineering and Balance

The engineering design of the horse figurine’s balance and inertial characteristics is of particular note. Unlike most ancient figurines designed with several points of support or a massive base (for example, the Minusinsk bell-shaped finials are stable due to a wide heavy base, and the Chinese tiger has a low center of gravity thanks to its crouched pose), the “Heavenly Horse” is intentionally depicted as a galloping horse supported by a minimum number of points. The stability of this composition was achieved by optimally distributing the figure’s mass. Computational analysis of inertia using the 3D model showed

that the main axial moment of inertia is oriented vertically, while the smallest is almost exactly in the horizontal “leap” plane. This means that the maximum inertia is concentrated along the vertical, preventing unwanted tilting, while in the plane of the leap, resistance to rotation is minimized, creating the effect of a stable “floating” pose. These proportions are unlikely to be accidental: statistical comparison with randomly shaped models showed that such a precise mass distribution is nearly impossible without intentional design. Thus, the ancient sculptor shifted the center of gravity and axes of inertia to give the piece dynamic equilibrium corresponding to a real galloping horse. The compared objects do not show such complex “engineering of form”—they are either static or stabilized differently, although they also have their own logic of balance. For example, standing goats on Saka finials are made thicker at the bottom, shifting their mass downward, and the tiger finial was likely attached to a shaft with a heavy socket. However, there is no evidence of such deliberate optimization of pose according to the laws of physics. The “Heavenly Horse,” in contrast, combines artistic concept with technical precision and careful calculation of inertial properties, setting it apart even from artifacts with similar subjects.

The combined comparative characteristics indicate that the bronze “Heavenly Horse” integrates technical and stylistic achievements from different cultural traditions into a single expressive image.

6. Conclusions

This study offers a comprehensive analysis of how galloping horses have been depicted in art from prehistory through Antiquity, with special attention to the Greco-Bactrian gilt bronze finial known as the “Heavenly Horse.” By systematically classifying main gallop motifs—the rearing gallop, flying gallop, landing gallop, and V-gallop—and comparing their occurrence across different cultures, we have shown that while stylized images dominated much of ancient art, realistic portrayals based on direct observation also existed and can be identified through close morphological and biomechanical analysis.

A central focus of the article is the anatomical and technical study of the Heavenly Horse finial, which demonstrates an unusually accurate three-dimensional depiction of the V-gallop suspension phase. High-resolution 3D scanning and computational inertia-tensor analysis confirm that the sculpture’s mass distribution and pose are purposefully optimized for stability and realism. These findings suggest a sophisticated practical knowledge of equine biomechanics among ancient artisans, predating modern motion photography.

In addition to anatomical accuracy, the sculpture integrates a range of symbolic and cultural markers. Features such as the single frontal protuberance (jibbah), S-shaped spine, and vine-and-cloud motif connect the artifact to descriptions of elite horse breeds in both Chinese and Central Asian sources, as well as to wider traditions of imperial and celestial symbolism across Eurasia. Comparative analysis with Saka and Chinese artifacts highlights both shared conventions (such as negative space and stylized ornament) and distinctive technical achievements, including the unique optimization of pose and balance in the Heavenly Horse.

Methodologically, this article is among the first to apply a combined protocol of mirrored-mesh asymmetry, power spectral density analysis, mesh-density heterogeneity, and computational inertia-tensor modeling to an ancient equine sculpture. This approach provides a reproducible visual and technical baseline for identifying realistic V-gallop features and detecting hand-modeled versus machine-made objects. The operationalization of historical metaphors, such as the Han-era “tiger’s back” as a biomechanical S-curve, further links textual and material evidence.

These digital methods extend the art-historical analysis in three concrete ways. First, they make visible technical features that are difficult to assess by visual inspection alone, such as left–right asymmetry, surface-density variation, and the absence of regular machine-tool patterns. Second, they convert formal observations about pose and balance into measurable parameters, allowing the V-gallop configuration and the sculpture’s inertial organization to be tested rather than only described. Third, they provide a reproducible framework for comparing this object with future scanned artifacts, making it possible to distinguish hand-modeled variation, workshop practice, and intentional engineering of form more systematically than traditional stylistic comparison alone.

Contextualizing the artifact within the broader history of horse exchange and symbolism along the Silk Road, the study shows that the Heavenly Horse finial embodies both the empirical observation of animal movement and the transmission of cosmological and political ideas. The sculpture’s combination of technical skill, anatomical precision, and layered symbolism reflects the dynamic cultural exchanges that shaped Eurasian art and statecraft.

The object may therefore have had a more complex role than that of a purely ornamental terminal. Its gilding, formal prominence, and cosmologically charged imagery suggest that it occupied a focal position within an elite ceremonial or ritual setting, where sovereignty, celestial order, and specialized knowledge were closely intertwined.

Future research should extend this interdisciplinary approach to other artifacts, particularly from lesser-known Silk Road contexts. Applying advanced imaging and modeling techniques can further clarify how ancient artists balanced realism, function, and meaning in their work, and how these choices were shaped by cross-cultural interactions.

In summary, the Heavenly Horse finial is not only a rare example of anatomical accuracy in ancient art but also a material witness to the convergence of artistic, scientific, and symbolic traditions across Eurasia. Its study contributes to our understanding of how the representation of animals in motion can serve as a lens on broader processes of technological innovation, cultural exchange, and ideological expression in the ancient world.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Notes

- ¹ The *Jockey of Artemision* statue is on display at the National Archaeological Museum, Athens, Greece, Room 34, inv. no. X 15177.
- ² The *Jockey of Artemision* statue is dated to 140 B.C. by the National Archaeological Museum of Athens but to 146 B.C. by Hemingway. Hemingway describes the extended discussion surrounding the question of whether it is more Classical or Hellenistic in style, or even a pastiche created in imitation of one such style, viewpoints which influence the interpretation of its dating (Hemingway 2004, pp. 83–89).
- ³ Examples of the Chinese Tang Dynasty polo equestrian statues can be found in: Musée Guimet, Paris, France, inv. no. MA 6115–6121; Cleveland Museum of Art, Cleveland, Ohio, USA, Severance and Greta Millikin Collection, inv. no. 1964.181; San Diego Museum of Art, San Diego, California, USA, inv. no. DSC 06493; and Xi’an Museum, Xi’an, China, on display; Montreal Museum of Fine Arts, Montreal, Canada, inv. no. DSC 09629.
- ⁴ Examples of the rearing gallop in early Egyptian art can be seen in the Cairo Museum, Egypt, inv. no. JE 61467; the Brooklyn Museum, Brooklyn, New York, USA, inv. no. 60.28.6; and in the tomb of Userhat (TT 56) in Thebes, Egypt. See facsimile of the latter in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, NY, USA, Gallery 135, inv. 30.4.42.
- ⁵ Such Assyrian reliefs with depictions of horses in a rearing gallop are quite common in the British Museum, London, UK, inv. no. 1856,0909.15, 1856,0909.36, and 1856,0909.48, items 118907, 124856, 124874–124876, and 124939a.
- ⁶ Examples of Classical Greek amphora with depictions of horses in a rearing gallop in celebration of Panathenaic Game victories or battles can be found in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA, inv. no. 07.128.1, 07.286.65, 07.286.79, 07.286.80, 07.286.84, 20.60.32, 52.11.17, 56.171.3, 56.171.4, 56.171.5, and 90.9.7; and the British Museum, London, UK, inv. no. 1903.0217.1. See also the relief of a chariot pulled by horses from Cyzicus, Anatolia (ca. 530 BC) also located at the Istanbul Archaeological Museum, Istanbul, Turkey, inv. no. 2813 T.
- ⁷ An example of such art can be found in the Louvre, Paris, France, inv. no. MA 836.
- ⁸ The relief of Alexander the Great hunting on a horse can be found in the Louvre, Paris, France, inv. no. MA 858.
- ⁹ The Bronze sculpture of Alexander the Great on Bucephalus is housed in the Naples Archaeological Museum, Naples, Italy, inv. no. 4996. Not surprisingly, Renaissance paintings of Alexander the Great on horseback also show him on a horse in a rearing gallop, as with *Le livre et la vraie hystoire du bon roy Alixandre* (ca. 1420–1425) and *Le livre des fais d’Alexandre le Grant* (ca. 1475), The paintings of Alexander on horseback from the *Le livre et la vraie hystoire du bon roy Alixandre* and *Le livre des fais d’Alexandre le Grant* can both be found in the British Library, London, UK, Royal MS 20 B XX, fol. 53r and Royal MS 17 F I, fol. 55r.
- ¹⁰ Parthian clay reliefs showing archers on horseback can be seen in the British Museum, London, inv. no. 1972,0229.1, item 135684; Staatlichen Museen, Berlin, Germany, inv. no. 3685; and the Cleveland Museum of Art, Cleveland, Ohio, USA, inv. no. 1970.15.
- ¹¹ Now found in the Istanbul Archaeological Museum, Istanbul, Turkey, inv. no. 73.7 T.
- ¹² The relief of the chariot race is in the British Museum, London, UK, inv. no. 1805,0703.337.
- ¹³ These statues from the Herculaneum Theater are found in the Naples Archaeological Museum, Naples, Italy, inv. no. 4894 and 5497.
- ¹⁴ Located in the Landesmuseum für Kärnten, Klagenfurt, Austria, inv. no. LM f K. See also equestrian illustration located in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA, inv. no. 49.97.327; the statue in the Museo Archeologico dei Campi Flegrei nel Castello di Baia in Bicoli, Italy, inv. no. 155743; the Renaissance illustration of the *Equus Domitiani* located in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA, inv. no. 49.95.1002(12); and the Barberini Ivory in the Louvre, Paris, France, inv. no. OA 9063.
- ¹⁵ See scenes no. 2, 11, 13, 17–18, 39–41, 48, 50–51, and 55–58 of the Bayeux Tapestry, located in the Musée de la Tapissierie, Bayeux, France.
- ¹⁶ See these seals of nobles in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA, inv. no. 23.240.4, and in the British Museum, London, inv. no. 1841,0624.1.
- ¹⁷ See the *Aberdeen Bestiary* housed at the University of Aberdeen, Aberdeen, Scotland, MS 24, fol. 8r.
- ¹⁸ See the illustrated edition of *Der Stricker’s Karl der Große* can be found in the Gallen Stiftsbibliothek, St. Gallen, Switzerland, MS Vad. 302 II, fol. 35v.
- ¹⁹ See the *Taymouth Hours* manuscript located in the British Library, London, UK, Yates Thompson Manuscript 13, fol. 78v and 79v.
- ²⁰ See the edition of the *Grandes Chroniques de France* found in the British Library, London, UK, Royal Manuscript 16 G vi, fol. 15r.
- ²¹ See the colorful painting of jousting knights by Barthélemy d’Eyck in the illustrated edition of René de Anjou’s *Livre de tournois*, housed in the Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris, France, MS Fr2695, fol. 2v–3r.
- ²² The painting is from the *Roman du Saint Graal* found in the Bibliothèque Municipale, Dijon, France, MS 527, fol. 5v.
- ²³ See the scene in the *Talbot-Shrewsbury Book*, British Library, Royal MS 15 E VI, fol. 21r.
- ²⁴ As noted above, Tang Dynasty polo horse and rider statues can be observed in the Musée Guimet, Paris, France, inv. no. MA 6116–6121; Cleveland Museum of Art, Cleveland, Ohio, USA, Severance and Greta Millikin Collection, inv. no. 1964.181; San Diego Museum of Art, San Diego, California, inv. no. DSC 06493; and in the Xi’an Museum, Xi’an, China, where they are on display.

- 25 Now on display in the Beilin Museum, Xi'an, Shaanxi Province, China.
- 26 Now in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA, inv. no. 1982.3.1.
- 27 Now housed in the Cleveland Museum of Art, Cleveland, Ohio, USA, inv. no. 1915.680.
- 28 Located in the National Archaeological Museum, Athens, Greece, inv. no. 240, 748, and 1428.
- 29 See the Persian Sasanian depiction of a hunting king (ca. 485–530) at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA, on display in gallery 202, inv. no. 34.33; the Persian Rostam Cycle mural from the Blue Hall at Penjikent, Tajikistan, ca. 725, which can now be found in the State Hermitage Museum, St. Petersburg, Russia, Hall 49. Also see illuminated manuscripts of Ferdowsi's Shahnameh including the Shahnameh of Shan Tahmasp, ca. 1535, Aga Khan Museum, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, MS AKM903, fol. 42r, the Peck Shahnameh, ca. 1590, Princeton University Library, Princeton, New Jersey, USA, Islamic MS 310, fol. 229r, and the Kangra Shahnameh, Kangra, India, 1695, at the Chester Beatty Library, CBL In 36, fol. 263r. There is also a Persian painting of the sixteenth century showing some horses in the background in a flying gallop in the British Museum, London, inv. no. 1930,0607,0.10.
- 30 Now in the Louvre, Paris, France, Sully Wing, Room 301.
- 31 Now in the British Museum, London, UK, inv. no. 1856,0909.47, item 124875.
- 32 Located in the Museo Civico Archeologico, Bologna, Italy, inv. no. 1889.
- 33 This item can be found in Gallery 119 of the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA, inv. no. 26.7.1293.
- 34 Currently on display in the Campania Romana Gallery of the Naples Archaeological Museum, Naples, Italy, items no. 2 and 11, in contrast with items no. 1, 5, and 9 where horses are more clearly seen in a rearing gallop.
- 35 Bayeux Tapestry, scene 54, Musée de la Tapisserie, Bayeux, France. See also illustration found in the Parker Library, Corpus Christi College, Cambridge, UK, MS 16, fol. 8r.
- 36 Some of these more realistic depictions of the landing phase of the galloping horse can be seen at the Virginia Museum of Fine Arts, Richmond, Virginia, USA, inv. no. 81.55 and 81.89; and the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA, inv. no. 06.1021.240, 26.60.31 (Roman artwork likely based on earlier classical Greek model), and 96.9.10.
- 37 Housed in the National Archaeological Museum of Naples, Naples, Italy, inv. no. 10020.
- 38 Found in the National Archaeological Museum of Athens, Athens, Greece, inv. no. 2715.
- 39 See the horse in the foreground in the Persian painting located in the British Museum, London, UK, inv. no. 1930,0607,0.10. See also the realistic Safavid Persian portrayals of the horse galloping as in an illuminated picture of Shah Isma'il on an Equestrian Hunting Expedition (ca. 1685), Harvard Art Museum, Cambridge, MA, USA, inv. no. 2005.201.
- 40 On display in the Luoyang Ancient Tombs Museum, Luoyang, Henan Province, China.
- 41 One of these tomb artworks is viewable at the Cincinnati Museum of Art, Cincinnati, Ohio, USA, inv. no. 1950.74.
- 42 This item can be found in the Victoria and Albert Museum, London, UK, inv. no. E.33–1964.
- 43 Stored in the British Library, Royal MS 20 B XX, fol. 12r and 53r.
- 44 In Chinese historical texts—especially during the Han dynasty—this kind of horses are often called “Dayuan horses” because they were imported from the kingdom of Dayuan, located in the Ferghana Valley.
- 45 Some modern horse breeds, such as the Moyle, Datong, Carthusian, and Chartreux are known to have double protuberances on their forehead (Chubb 1934; Rousseau 2017, 94 and 460). However, the single forehead protuberance or frontal boss is rare and only found on some Arabian and Caspian horses (Hendricks 1995, 113–114 and 294; Rousseau 2017, 290 and 296–297).
- 46 This artifact is located in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, USA, inv. no. 47.719.
- 47 Units & density. Linear dimensions were converted from millimeters ($1 \text{ mm} \rightarrow 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$). Unless stated otherwise, absolute inertias are reported under $\rho = 1$ (unit density) for consistency with the manuscript; adopting a physical bronze density ($\rho \approx 7800 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) scales (I_1, I_2, I_3) linearly (e.g., for the ~300 k-face model: $\approx 0.005764, 0.013182, 0.018564 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$), while ratios and angles ($I_1/I_3, I_2/I_3$; the $\sim 0.20^\circ$ tilt of the I_1 -axis) remain unchanged. The principal-axis geometry and the hierarchy $I_1 < I_2 < I_3$ are dictated by the external shape; any internal cavity would shift absolute numbers but not the qualitative conclusions—future work can model wall thickness via an offset-shell or verify with ultrasonic thickness before rerunning the calculations. Robustness was evaluated with topology-preserving quadratic decimation ($4.09 \text{ M} \rightarrow \approx 300 \text{ k faces}$), which left I-values within $< 0.02\%$ and the I_1 -tilt within $< 0.0001^\circ$; we did not use random face drops because they break watertightness and bias mass properties. Baseline A is an illustrative (not universal) comparison class that holds volume/mass fixed and varies side-ratios around the finial's AABB. As an empirical check, a homogeneous 3D-printed prototype stood stably and did not topple, consistent with the inertial inference.
- 48 Field imaging (including UVF/NIR) and 3D modeling were performed in the United States, while processing and analysis were conducted in Kazakhstan in collaboration with a partner university laboratory.

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